

From Silence to Dialogue: The Individual and Societal Impacts of Events by Jäbät ja Tunteet

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Affidavit

I hereby declare that I have written this Master's Thesis independently and without outside help and that I have not used any sources or aids other than those indicated in the editing and writing process, and that I have marked verbatim and analogous quotations as such. This Master's Thesis has not been submitted elsewhere for examination purposes.

Vienna, May 11, 2025

Use of artificial intelligence and large language models (LLM)

ChatGPT of OpenAI was used for proofreading (linguistic and stylistic revision) of the self-written text. No changes or additions were made to the content.

Vienna, May 11, [2025](#)

Acknowledgment

In loving memory of Janne Puhakka (1995–2024), a dear colleague, friend, and role model.

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List of Abbreviations

CPM Critical Positive Masculinity

SIT Social Identity Theory

Abstract

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Abstract of the Master Thesis “From Silence to Dialogue: The Individual and Societal Impacts of Events by Jäbät ja Tunteet”

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This thesis explores how the Finnish community Jäbät ja Tunteet promotes emotional expression and challenges dominant masculinity norms through its Conversation Clubs. Drawing on qualitative interviews with nine participants, the study investigates the individual and societal benefits of attending these male-only peer support events. The research applies Masculinity Theory, Critical Positive Masculinity and Social Identity Theory to examine how structured, emotionally supportive environments can foster personal growth and cultural transformation.

Thematic analysis revealed that participants experienced increased emotional literacy, trust, and community belonging. These clubs not only helped men better understand and express their emotions, but also encouraged them to carry these practices into broader social contexts, creating ripple effects in friendships, families, and workplaces. The clubs were found to act both as sites of healing and as catalysts for cultural change—offering a counter-narrative to hegemonic masculinity. However, challenges remain in reaching more emotionally disengaged men and in balancing self-reflection with broader social responsibility.

This study contributes to academic discussions in gender studies, culture and event management, and community engagement. It also offers practical insights for organizers and facilitators aiming to design inclusive, transformative event formats that support healthier emotional norms among men.

1. Introduction

Have you seen your father cry more than five times during your lifetime? In fact, have you seen him express anything other than the so-called football feelings – joy and anger? Most of us have not.

We live in a world with escalating violence, mental health crises, deepening polarization, and ingrained gender inequalities. Globally, acts of violence are not only persistent but evolving in complexity, and a silent epidemic known as the mental health crisis is unfolding—particularly among men, who are far less likely to seek help (United Nations, 2021). This unaddressed pain often manifests outward, contributing to higher rates of violence and self-destruction. Simultaneously young men are drawn to political extremes, creating further division (Men and Masculinities, 2020). Social media has become a battlefield where ideologies clash and algorithms drive wedges between us (Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences, 2021). In this fractured landscape, the battle for gender equality remains an urgent fight. The public discourse on “toxic” and “healthy” masculinity highlights a society struggling to shed its old ways (Men and Masculinities, 2020).

In recent years, several grassroots communities have emerged globally, aiming to support men in expressing vulnerability and navigating emotional challenges. One such example is Jäbät ja Tunteet (Dudes and Feelings), a Finnish initiative that organizes open Conversation Clubs for men to reflect on feelings, masculinity, and relationships in a safe, facilitated environment. This study explores the significance of these gatherings, focusing on how such events may influence individual behavior and social norms. A more detailed overview of the case and related initiatives is presented in Chapter 2.

1.1 Objective and Research question

The main objective of this research is to analyze the individual and societal benefits of the events organized by Jäbät ja Tunteet. The thesis seeks to understand how

participation in these events affects attendees' emotional intelligence, mental well-being, and perceptions of masculinity. It also seeks to assess how effectively these events encourage positive behavioral changes, which could, in turn, help address some of the ongoing challenges in both society and within the event and cultural sector.

This research is guided by the following research question:

RQ: What are the individual and societal benefits of the events organized by Jäbät ja Tunteet?

This research question was selected because it addresses a meaningful topic at the intersection of gender, mental health, and peer support. It allows for an exploration of both personal experiences and broader cultural dynamics, offering valuable insights for understanding the role of events by Jäbät ja Tunteet in shaping emotional expression and community well-being.

1.2 Purpose and relevance

Events are key cultural sites where social norms are both reinforced and challenged (Quinn, 2013). Analyzing the role of events organized by Jäbät ja Tunteet offers insights into how cultural norms around masculinity and emotional expression are actively negotiated and redefined. The study highlights how these events serve as platforms for social change, providing space for reflection, dialogue, and transformation. Such research is essential in understanding the cultural dynamics within event-based settings and their potential to influence broader societal norms.

This research contributes to ongoing discussions on how community-based events can be leveraged to challenge toxic masculinity and promote more inclusive, emotionally supportive norms. Additionally, it underscores the importance of addressing cultural norms surrounding masculinity and the stigma associated with male emotional expression, as these often reflect broader societal dynamics.

2. Case Study & Context

To better understand the setting and relevance of this study, this chapter presents the case of Jäbät ja Tunteet in detail. This case is situated within a broader landscape of male support communities, some of which share similar goals but differ in focus, format, and audience. By first outlining the structure and values of Jäbät ja Tunteet, and then briefly comparing it to two prominent international initiatives—Men’s Shed and Andy’s Man Club—this chapter provides the contextual foundation for exploring how such movements foster emotional growth and social change.

2.1. Jäbät ja Tunteet

The Finnish community Jäbät ja Tunteet offers a constructive outlet for men to enhance emotional wellbeing and engage in personal growth (Jäbät ja Tunteet, n.d.). Founded by Nosh A Lody and friends, the community began as meaningful conversations within their social circle, eventually evolving into a podcast in January 2021. A year later, reflecting on the collective strength of community, the founders expanded their mission to include live events, establishing Jäbät ja Tunteet as a hub for men’s dialogue in Finland. Today, they describe themselves as a “dude community and media.” Through online spaces, weekly Conversation Clubs, a widely listen-to podcast, and an active Instagram presence with around 10.000 followers, they aim to help men “feel more and feel better.”

The Conversation Clubs operate in four cities across Finland and are free of charge, with no registration or membership required. In Helsinki—where the concept has developed longest—15 to 25 participants typically attend each week (J. Härkönen, personal communication, February 20, 2025). In other cities, participation varies between smaller groups of 5 to 15. Each event centers around a predefined theme such as shame, anger, or identity. These themes are selected based on current relevance, participant suggestions, Telegram community discussions, and occasionally through collaborations with commercial partners. The clubs are facilitated by volunteers who prepare the space, welcome participants, and divide them into small discussion groups. Aside from that, facilitators take part as equals; they do not guide the conversations, aligning with the community’s non-hierarchical form.

The community is governed by a core team of four organizers who rotate every two years to bring in fresh perspectives and avoid stagnation. Former organizers often stay involved in a more advisory capacity. Jäbät ja Tunteet ry is registered as a non-profit organization, while a limited company (Jäbät Oy) handles commercial partnerships and funding acquisition to sustain the community. A code of conduct ensures mutual respect, emotional safety, and confidentiality within the clubs.

Participants are primarily men aged 20 to 35, with diversity in cultural backgrounds. Speaking Finnish is not a requirement to participate, since the conversations can also be held in English. The community positions itself against traditional masculine ideals rooted in stoicism and silence. One of their most important goals is to break the intergenerational cycle in which harmful models of masculinity and a culture of silence are passed from father to son. In doing so, they aim to create healthy, diverse ways of being a man (Mahadura, 2022). In recent years, the community has also organized occasional events open to all genders; however, this study focuses exclusively on the Conversation Club format.

Jäbät ja Tunteet can be seen as a social movement with the potential to influence cultural norms. A social movement is defined as “a sustained campaign of claim making, using repeated performances that advertise the claim, based on organizations, networks, traditions, and solidarities that sustain these activities” (Tilly & Tarrow, 2007, p. 8). Advocating for emotional openness and challenging hegemonic masculinity aligns with the requirement of claim-making, while activities such as the podcast, weekly events, and public-facing Conversation Clubs at festivals and student gatherings fulfill the criteria of repeated performances. The structured organization and consistent presence across platforms support its characterization as a contemporary, culturally rooted social movement.

2.2 Comparable Initiatives

Jäbät ja Tunteet is not the only ongoing movement of its kind. Men’s Shed is a community-based movement that provides men with a space to socialize, work on practical projects, and support one another’s well-being. Originating in Australia in the 1990s, it aims to fight social isolation and mental health issues among men,

particularly older men, by fostering a sense of purpose, community, and shared skills. The initiative has since expanded globally, promoting peer support, informal conversations, and emotional well-being in a setting where men feel comfortable engaging in meaningful activities (Men's Shed, n.d.). Research on Men's Sheds has provided valuable insight into the participants and outcomes associated with these initiatives. Golding (2015) reviewed over 100 studies published between 1995 and 2014, finding that participants were typically older, retired, or unemployed men, with lower levels of formal education, often living in rural areas. His review, along with Wilson & Cordier (2013), highlights that the main benefits of Men's Sheds are enhanced social interaction, new friendships, and opportunities for learning new skills, with limited evidence for broader health and well-being improvements. Further studies suggest that engaging in traditionally male activities provides a context where men feel more comfortable opening up emotionally in conversations with peers (Milligan et al., 2013; 2015). However, while these settings foster emotional openness and trust among participants, research also suggests that such emotional practices may be difficult to carry into everyday life beyond the group (Wilson & Cordier, 2013; Golding, 2015). The structured safety and shared norms of these communities provide a unique context that may not be easily replicated in more conventional male environments. Mackenzie et al. (2017) explored how participants in Canadian Men's Sheds discussed masculinity, using a gender relations framework. The study focused on how their conversations reflected both traditional hegemonic ideals and more flexible, alternative views of masculinity. The findings suggest that while many participants supported dominant masculine norms, there was also openness to more fluid understandings of masculinity, especially once trust and strong relationships had been established.

Andy's Man Club is a UK-based mental health support group for men, founded in 2016 after the suicide of Andy Roberts, a young man struggling with mental health issues. The organization provides free, non-judgmental, peer-led spaces where men can openly talk about their feelings and challenges. Their goal is to break the stigma around male mental health and reduce suicide rates by fostering a supportive community. The meetings are confidential and inclusive, encouraging men to share

their experiences in a safe environment. The motto #itsokaytotalk reflects their mission to normalize emotional expression among men (Andy's Man Club, n.d.).

While Men's Shed and Andy's Man Club share similarities with Jäbät ja Tunteet in providing safe spaces for men to connect and talk, their core focus differs. Both Men's Shed and Andy's Man Club are centered around mental health support, with the latter specifically aiming to prevent suicide and provide crisis support. In contrast, Jäbät ja Tunteet focuses more on fostering healthy emotional expression as a proactive practice rather than a response to severe mental health struggles. Additionally, the participants of Jäbät ja Tunteet tends to be younger, and they are not only seeking personal growth but also actively working to reshape societal perceptions of masculinity.

3. Literature Review

Understanding the history of gender studies, the evolution of masculinities, and past social movements provides crucial context for this study. It allows the case of Jäbät ja Tunteet to be examined not as an isolated phenomenon, but as part of a broader cultural and historical shift in how masculinity is expressed, negotiated, and reshaped.

3.1 Gender Studies & Hegemonic Masculinity

The field of gender studies emerged in response to feminist scholarship, particularly from the mid-20th century onward, with influential thinkers like Simone de Beauvoir (1953) and Judith Butler (1990) challenging traditional conceptions of gender. While initially centered on women's rights and experiences, the field later expanded to include studies on men and masculinities. In the 1980s, scholars such as Connell (1987) and Kimmel (1996) initiated masculinity studies, laying the groundwork for understanding masculinity as a social construct shaped by cultural norms and power dynamics.

The concept of hegemonic masculinity refers to the culturally dominant ideal of manhood, characterized by emotional suppression, competitiveness, and authority (Connell, 1987; Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005). This model establishes a hierarchy among men and between genders, privileging certain traits while marginalizing others.

Donaldson (1993) argues that hegemonic masculinity operates through consensus, appearing “natural” even though it is socially produced. Traditional masculinity norms did not emerge in a vacuum, but were historically shaped by broader social structures, such as the industrial revolution, gendered divisions of labor, and post-war societal expectations. Scholars such as Kimmel (1996) have emphasized how economic, social, and political changes have continuously influenced what it means to be a man, with industrialization and war reinforcing ideals of stoicism, independence, and emotional restraint. While masculinity can take many different forms, Pleck (1995) emphasized that there is a recognizable pattern of expectations tied to the traditional male role across Western societies. According to Levant (1996), this traditional masculinity ideology represented the prevailing model of manhood prior to the feminist challenges to gender roles that gained momentum during the 1960s and 1970s. While often associated with negative traits, Connell and Messerschmidt (2005) emphasize that hegemonic masculinity is not inherently toxic — it evolves over time and can potentially incorporate more balanced and emotionally expressive forms of masculinity. The concept has been influential in a variety of fields, from psychotherapy and violence prevention (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005) to criminology (Bufkin, 1999; Messerschmidt, 1997), helping to contextualize patterns of male aggression and emotional disconnection.

3.2 Stigma and Emotional Suppression

Building on the concept of hegemonic masculinity, it is important to examine how emotional suppression and stigma have shaped men’s emotional lives. Gender norms, particularly those stemming from hegemonic masculinity, have long contributed to the stigma surrounding emotional expression — especially among men. As Corrigan (2005) notes, stigma operates as a social structure that regulates behavior by defining what is acceptable within a group. In many Western societies, masculinity is associated with emotional control, reinforcing the idea that vulnerability is a weakness (Connell, 1987).

However, emotional suppression is not an innate male trait. Rather, emotional expression is a learned behavior shaped by cultural context and socialization (Holmes,

2015). Historically, emotional restraint was valued for both men and women in European societies from the Middle Ages into the early modern period (Elias [1939] 2000). Over time, however, emotional regulation became increasingly gendered, with men expected to embody ideals of stoicism and self-control (Connell, 1987). Seidler (2007) and Connell (2000) argue that while men are equally capable of emotional reflexivity, societal expectations continue to restrict their willingness to express vulnerability. While maintaining emotional distance has been culturally valued among men, men clearly benefit from strong relations to other men (Cordier & Wilson, 2014; Golding, 2015). Despite this, men tend to have more difficulty than women in developing and maintaining close friendships (Richardson & Smith, 2011). Friendships between men have traditionally been shaped by norms of competition, policing, and social comparison (Kimmel, 1994). However, recent studies suggest a loosening of these expectations. Research around Inclusive Masculinity Theory, for instance, indicates that young, middle-class, white men are increasingly engaging in emotionally expressive friendships (Anderson, 2008; Anderson & McGuire, 2010).

Nonetheless, multiple studies have found that men are willing to express emotions when placed in non-judgmental, peer-based environments (Addis, 2011; Lomas, 2013; McQueen, 2017). Holmes (2015) argues that challenging stigma requires not only redefining masculinity but also creating spaces where emotional openness is modeled and normalized, stressing that talking about feelings needs to be practiced. Her research also shows that men tend to disclose more easily to female partners, though typically within certain emotional limits (Holmes, 2015). Interestingly, even in everyday male friendships, emotional conversations can occur, though often in more indirect or guarded forms (Gough et al., 2021). Men sometimes navigate emotional conversations by keeping discussions vague or downplaying vulnerability, thus balancing emotional expression with the need to conform to masculine norms. Gough et al. (2021) highlight that men do talk about emotions, but another question is whether others are willing to listen and encourage it.

Building trust appears to be crucial for more open emotional talk. Studies summarized by Gough et al. (2021) on men's use of online forums for discussing sensitive issues — such as depression, anxiety, and body image — emphasize that trust is a key factor

for enabling disclosure. Whether online or face-to-face, establishing a sense of shared ground is critical for men to feel safe enough to engage with emotional topics.

As Jamieson (1998) points out, the social expectation to share and disclose emotions is a relatively recent development, heavily shaped by the rise of therapeutic discourse in modern Western societies (Illouz, 2008). Yet for many men, vulnerability is still shaped by structural gender dynamics, as the patriarchal system both restricts men's emotional expression and reinforces their social advantages. This means that calls for male vulnerability are often layered with tensions around power, privilege, and gendered expectations (Connell, 1995; Bourdieu, 2001).

Encouraging men to be more emotionally expressive is often seen as progressive. However, scholars like de Boise (2015) caution that these appeals can sometimes mask deeper anxieties about men's changing roles in society. He argues that promoting emotional openness may serve to preserve traditional masculine ideals by allowing emotional expression only within certain acceptable boundaries, thus maintaining existing gender hierarchies. Building on this, McQueen (2017) identifies a tension between traditional and progressive discourses of male emotionality. She notes that men are caught between the enduring norm of emotional restraint — “boys don't cry” — and the newer expectation to be emotionally open — “it's good to talk.” This creates a complex landscape where men are encouraged to express emotions, but often only in ways that align with traditional masculine ideals of strength and control.

3.3 Movements and Social Change

Throughout history, movements have emerged to challenge traditional masculinity and promote alternative expressions of male identity. The Men's Liberation Movement in the 1960s and 1970s questioned rigid gender roles and emphasized the emotional costs of traditional masculinity for men (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005). The pro-feminist men's movement emerged in response to feminism, aiming to expose the diversity of masculinities and men's real experiences, while seeking to redefine masculinity in alignment with feminist critiques of patriarchy (Gates, 2012). In contrast, the Mythopoetic Men's Movement, led by figures like Robert Bly, focused on reclaiming

an “authentic” masculinity through myth, ritual, and storytelling (Gilbert, 1992). Though ideologically diverse, these movements collectively marked a shift toward acknowledging the restrictive nature of hegemonic norms and laid the foundation for contemporary grassroots efforts like Jäbät ja Tunteet. While these earlier movements combined personal reflection with political activism, contemporary initiatives like Jäbät ja Tunteet focus more on emotional well-being and community support. Earlier movements aimed to challenge not just masculine norms but also broader structures of male privilege. In contrast, today's movements tend to emphasize creating safe, non-confrontational spaces where emotional openness is encouraged through peer support and storytelling, rather than direct political action.

According to Melucci (1996), contemporary social movements are not only political in nature but also cultural, seeking to redefine collective identities and everyday practices. In this sense, Jäbät ja Tunteet reflects what Melucci describes as a “movement of meaning,” which refers to movements that aim to transform cultural understandings and reshape the ways individuals relate to one another in daily life. By challenging internalized norms and offering a new emotional language for Finnish men, Jäbät ja Tunteet seeks to shift how masculinity and emotional expression are understood in both personal and collective contexts.

3.4 Research Gap

The existing research clearly shows that hegemonic masculinity and stigma have constrained men’s emotional expression. Although emotional barriers have been studied in contexts like romantic relationships, therapy, and online communication, relatively little research has examined grassroots, peer-led, face-to-face initiatives (Gough & Robertson, 2021).

Projects like Men’s Shed, Andy’s Man Club, and Jäbät ja Tunteet show increasing interest in these kinds of community-based spaces. Studies on Men’s Shed, for example, have demonstrated benefits around social connection, skill-building, and informal emotional support (Golding, 2015; Wilson & Cordier, 2013). While Mackenzie et al. (2017) found some openness toward more fluid forms of masculinity

among Canadian Men's Shed members, broader cultural impacts and shifts in masculine identity within these initiatives remain underexplored.

This study seeks to fill that gap by focusing on Jäbät ja Tunteet as a case study of emotional engagement, peer support, and social change. Specifically, it investigates how the structure, facilitation, and atmosphere of the Conversation Clubs shape men's emotional openness and their views on masculinity. The findings aim to contribute to the fields of gender studies, community development, and event design, offering insight into how intentionally designed social environments can challenge traditional masculine norms and foster emotional growth.

This review of the existing literature lays the groundwork for the theoretical framework, which will further inform the analysis of Jäbät ja Tunteet's events in the following chapter.

4. Theoretical framework

This chapter presents the theoretical framework for analyzing how events by Jäbät ja Tunteet influences men's emotional expression and identity formation. The selected theories—Masculinity Theory, Critical Positive Masculinity (CPM), and Social Identity Theory (SIT)—each offer unique insights. Masculinity Theory provides a foundation for understanding traditional and evolving gender norms, CPM highlights constructive approaches to masculinity, and SIT explains how group membership shapes individual and collective behavior. Together, these theories create a multidimensional lens for examining the impact of the Conversation Clubs on emotional well-being and societal change.

4.1 Masculinity Theory

Masculinity theory has been central to gender studies, particularly through the concept of hegemonic masculinity, which, as introduced in the literature review, defines the dominant, socially valued form of masculinity (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005). This framework highlights how masculinity is shaped by cultural expectations around emotional restraint, strength, and autonomy, often discouraging men from openly

expressing vulnerability. This study builds on these concepts to examine how Jäbät ja Tunteet challenges these norms. However, critics argue that the theory overemphasizes social structures, making it less adaptable when looking at how masculinity is shaped through everyday actions and situations (Pitt & Fox, 2012).

4.2 Critical Positive Masculinity

Tim Lomas' concept of CPM, influenced by positive psychology, seeks to redefine masculinity by moving beyond toxic or hegemonic models and fostering healthier, more inclusive expressions of being a man (2013). CPM acknowledges the harmful aspects of traditional masculinity while emphasizing the potential for positive traits, such as emotional intelligence, care, and ethical responsibility. Rather than rejecting masculinity altogether, CPM encourages men to critically reflect on gender norms and actively reshape masculinity in a way that benefits both men and society. Lomas (2013) highlights that "some men are able to strategically navigate hegemonic norms - either resisting or redefining them - to fashion a more 'positive' masculine performance" (p. 178). However, CPM also builds on the Critical Studies on Men approach, acknowledging that even seemingly positive forms of masculinity can still reinforce power imbalances and disadvantage marginalized groups. By balancing critique with optimism, CPM offers a perspective that neither assumes masculinity is inherently harmful nor naively idealizes change but instead considers the realistic potential for positive transformation. While CPM is a relatively new concept rather than a fully established theory, it provides a modern perspective by a researcher who has studied masculinity and found some limitations in existing theories.

4.3 Social Identity Theory

SIT, developed by Tajfel & Turner (1979), explains how individuals define themselves based on group membership. The theory suggests that people gain self-esteem from their social identities, leading to in-group favoritism and differentiation from out-groups. Through social categorization, individuals classify themselves and others into groups, shaping behavior and self-perception. Social identification reinforces group

cohesion, as members internalize shared norms and values, while social comparison strengthens belonging by contrasting one's group with others.

Although SIT has been highly influential in understanding group dynamics, it has faced substantial critique. Some scholars argue that it places too much emphasis on favoritism toward one's own group while not giving enough attention to negative attitudes toward other groups (Brown, 2000; Huddy, 2001). Others note that its broad scope makes it difficult to empirically test or falsify. In addition, the idea that people give up their personal identity to follow group norms may be overstated, as members often continue to hold a range of individual views. In response, more recent research has refined the theory, recognizing that identity is fluid, and that individuals not only adopt group norms but also shape them (Turner & Reynolds, 2012). This shift has expanded SIT's applications beyond intergroup bias to include emotions, historical memory, justice, leadership, and political conflict (Haslam, 2014; Reicher et al., 2010). Today, researchers view groups as internally complex, where diverse perspectives and debates influence collective identity (Hogg, 2006). Despite its critiques, SIT remains a widely used framework across psychology and social sciences.

4.4 Integration of Theories

Masculinity theory provides a historical and cultural foundation for understanding how traditional norms shape men's emotional expression and how these norms can evolve. CPM moves beyond critiques of toxic masculinity, offering a constructive framework for analyzing *Jäbät ja Tunteet* as more than just a reaction to hegemonic masculinity—it presents a proactive redefinition of masculinity centered on emotional intelligence and well-being. SIT explains how group dynamics shape behavior, providing insight into why men feel safe expressing emotions in these Conversation Clubs and how shared identity fosters change.

Together, these theories create a multidimensional framework. Masculinity theory contextualizes the persistence of hegemonic masculinity, CPM highlights a critical yet optimistic approach to redefining masculinity, and SIT links individual experiences to broader group and societal processes. This combination allows for a comprehensive

analysis of Jäbät ja Tunteet, capturing the psychological, social, and cultural dimensions of its impact.

5. Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodology used in this study, detailing the assumptions, research design, data collection process, and data analysis techniques. It explains how participants were selected and interviewed, how the data was prepared and analyzed, and how the quality of the research was ensured. The chapter also reflects on the researcher's role and addresses the ethical considerations taken to protect participants and uphold the integrity of the study.

This study focuses on individuals who identify as men and explores masculinity in that context. While the terminology and analysis at times refer to binary gender distinctions (e.g., men vs. women), the researcher acknowledges that gender exists on a spectrum and that not all individuals identify within binary categories. The binary framing used here reflects the focus and structure of the research, not a belief in its universality.

5.1 Research Assumptions and Rationale

This study is guided by several key assumptions drawn from the theoretical framework and literature review, which shaped the methodological choices.

The literature suggests that hegemonic masculinity discourages men from emotional expression, reinforcing traditional expectations of what it means to be a man. Therefore, one core assumption is that men often struggle with emotional vulnerability, particularly in male-only groups. At the same time, research shows that emotional suppression is not an inherent male trait but a learned behavior, leading to the assumption that men can shift toward healthier and more positive forms of masculinity when provided with the right environment.

SIT further suggests that individuals adopt behaviors aligned with group norms, supporting the assumption that men may feel safer expressing emotions when surrounded by like-minded peers who normalize vulnerability.

These assumptions informed the research design in several ways. They justified the choice of a qualitative approach to explore the subjective experiences and perceived changes among participants. They also guided the use of purposive sampling to select individuals with sufficient engagement in the Conversation Clubs, as these participants were most likely to reflect on emotional and behavioral change. Finally, the assumptions shaped the use of reflexive thematic analysis, as this approach allows for exploring both individual and social processes, such as shifting masculine norms and group dynamics.

5.2 Research design

Creswell and Poth (2018) identify three main research strategies: quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods. In simple terms, quantitative research deals with numbers and statistical analysis, while qualitative research focuses on words, meanings, and complex social phenomena. Mixed methods combine both approaches. While quantitative data allows for measurement and generalization, qualitative research is better suited for exploring individual experiences and deeper contextual understanding. Given the focus of this study on the personal experiences and perceived effects of Jäbät ja Tunteet's events, a qualitative approach was chosen. This approach allowed for an in-depth exploration of participants' perspectives, providing rich, nuanced insights that quantitative methods would have been unable to capture.

Within qualitative research, case study methodology provides a structured way to examine real-world phenomena within their natural settings (Rowley, 2002; Yin, 2018). According to Yin (2014), different types of cases exist, including unique and representative cases. This case is not entirely unique, as similar movements, such as Men's Shed and Andy's Man Club, have been identified. However, it is also not a typical case that can be directly compared to others. Therefore, it falls somewhere between a unique and a representative case, serving as a pioneering and contemporary example of a grassroots movement that redefines masculinity through emotional openness. Since this phenomenon is ongoing, deeply embedded in social interactions, and cannot be experimentally manipulated, a case study enables an exploratory and interpretive approach, capturing participants lived experiences in depth (Stake, 1995).

Additionally, case studies are valuable for analyzing complex social processes and group dynamics, making them well-suited for examining the ways in which masculinity norms are challenged and reshaped within a peer-support setting (Merriam, 2009).

Case study research often incorporates multiple sources of data to enhance the depth and reliability of findings (Rowley, 2002). While additional data sources—such as detailed observations—could have added further insights, this study relies exclusively on interviews due to scope limitations and the sensitive nature of the topic. This choice allowed the researcher to focus on participants' own narratives, which were central to the research objective.

5.3 Data collection

For the data collection, the method of semi-structured interviews was chosen to gain in-depth insights and personal experiences which could have been difficult to access through other methods. As Seidman (2013) puts it, “at the root of in-depth interviewing is an interest in understanding the lived experience of other people and the meaning they make of that experience” (p. 9). Semi-structured interviews provided direct access to participants' perspectives, while also allowing flexibility to follow up on unexpected themes or insights (Skinner et al., 2015). This made them the most suitable method for understanding the subjective impact of the Conversation Clubs.

5.3.1 Sampling

This study employs purposive sampling, a non-random sampling technique where participants are selected based on specific criteria relevant to the research objective (Bryman, 2010). This approach ensured that the sample consisted of individuals who could provide rich, meaningful insights into the phenomenon being studied. In this case, participants were required to have attended at least five Jäbät ja Tunteet Conversation Clubs. This criterion was set to ensure that respondents had sufficient experience with the discussions, allowing for a deeper exploration of how the events influence emotional intelligence, communication, and perceptions of masculinity.

Importantly, participants were regarded as experts on the matter, not by formal credentials but through their lived experience and sustained engagement within the community. Having actively participated in multiple events, they were uniquely positioned to reflect on both the personal and social impacts of the Conversation Clubs. Their insights were therefore critical for answering the research question, which focuses on the individual and societal benefits of the events. Randomly sampling individuals with little involvement in the clubs would not have provided the depth of reflection and firsthand knowledge required to address these aims.

To find suitable interviewees, the organizers of the community were contacted by email. They passed on the message to the community Telegram channel, which contains more than 700 men. Nine people meeting the criteria were interviewed. The names are changed to keep the participants anonymous, but pseudonyms are used instead of, for example, “interviewee 1” to keep the analysis as humane as possible. The interviews were conducted over Microsoft Teams due to geographical restrictions and lasted between 26–43 minutes. Table 1 shows an overview of the conducted interviews, including an estimation of the number of Conversation Clubs the interviewees have participated in.

Table 1
Overview of conducted interviews

Date	Interviewee	Number of events	Duration of Interview
25.02.2025	David	25-30	37 min
25.02.2025	Anton	~15	30 min
26.02.2025	William	10-15	32 min
27.02.2025	John	6-9	31 min
03.03.2025	Tim	~10	26 min
03.03.2025	Mikeal	6-7	43 min
03.03.2025	Oliver	20-30	29 min
03.03.2025	Axel	~20	39 min
04.3.2025	Oscar	~15	26 min

The interviewees were given the opportunity to have the interview in Finnish, Swedish or English, in order for them to speak in their native language or the language they

were most comfortable with. Eight of the interviews were held in Finnish, and one in English.

5.3.2 Interview guide

The interview guide presented in Appendix 1 (English) and Appendix 2 (Finnish) was produced. The guide consisted of 19 questions divided into six sections, creating a structure for the interviews. The first introductory section focused on questions that ease the participants into the topic, while the second one focused on the events themselves, delving into things like atmosphere, experience, and the topics of the discussions. The focus of the third section lay in the personal impact of the events, while the fourth one allowed for discussion on influence on others. The fifth section sought reflections around cultural and societal impacts, while the sixth and final one wrapped up the interviews and allowed for participants to add anything they might have felt they did not have a chance to share through the proposed questions.

5.3.3 Transcription and translation

During the data collection process, the interviews were transcribed using Microsoft Teams' automatic transcription function. These transcriptions were then carefully corrected and edited manually by the researcher to ensure accuracy. Following transcription, the interviews were translated into English using the translation tool DeepL. The translations were then thoroughly revised and refined by the researcher to better reflect the intended meaning, as direct translations can sometimes obscure nuances in expression. The researcher's native fluency in the interview language contributed to a more nuanced and accurate translation, although the potential for translation bias remains. In addition to preparing the material for analysis, this process of transcription and translation also marked the initial stage of reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019), as it allowed the researcher to become deeply familiar with the data.

5.4 Data analysis

During this initial phase, early observations and notes were made, which later informed the development of themes. The subsequent phase of analysis involved generating

initial codes, where meaningful features of the data were identified and grouped. This process was conducted in MAXQDA, a qualitative data analysis software, which supported the organization and comparison of coded material across transcripts. Codes were developed through a combination of inductive and deductive approaches: while the coding was primarily data-driven (inductive), it was also informed by existing theoretical perspectives on masculinity, emotional expression, and peer support (deductive). Reflexive thematic analysis was chosen because it allows for the identification of both explicit content and underlying patterns, making it well suited for analyzing complex, socially embedded phenomena such as masculinity.

Following coding, the codes were collected into potential themes, considering how different codes combined to reflect broader patterns of meaning. As the analysis progressed, the researcher continuously refined and reviewed the themes to ensure they accurately reflected the data and addressed the research questions (Braun & Clarke, 2019). In the final stage, the themes were carefully named and defined to capture their central meanings and highlight their relevance to the study's aims. This stage of the process is documented in the codebook (Appendix 3), which provides an overview of the final codes, their definitions, and illustrative examples from the data. Including the codebook enhances the transparency and trustworthiness of the analysis by offering a clear record of how the themes were developed and grounded in the participants' accounts.

5.5 Quality of the research

This section discusses the measures taken to ensure the reliability, validity, and overall quality of the research. The role of the researcher and ethical considerations are also presented.

5.5.1 Reliability and Validity

In qualitative research, reliability refers to the consistency of the research process. This study ensured reliability by using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019), which involves a systematic and transparent approach to data analysis. A consistent interview guide was used across all participants to maintain comparability, and the

data were analyzed systematically using MAXQDA software, supporting a clear and structured coding process. Additionally, the transcripts were carefully corrected after the automatic transcription, and the translations were refined to preserve the participants' intended meanings, further strengthening the consistency of the research.

Validity focuses on the accuracy and authenticity of the data. To enhance validity, the analysis was grounded in the participants' own words, and codes and themes were developed based on both inductive insights from the data and deductive input from relevant theory (Braun & Clarke, 2019). Using direct quotes in the reporting helped to authentically represent the participants' voices. Triangulation was applied by combining diverse participant perspectives and integrating inductive and deductive analytical approaches. Regarding generalizability, it is important to note that qualitative research typically does not aim for statistical generalization (Bryman, 2010). Instead, this study followed the idea of analytic generalization (Yin, 2009), seeking to link the findings to theoretical concepts so they may offer insights beyond the specific case.

Furthermore, the study addressed aspects of credibility, transferability, and confirmability to enhance the overall trustworthiness of the research. Credibility was strengthened by reflecting the participants' perspectives through direct quotations and careful theme development. Transferability was supported by providing detailed descriptions of the research context and sample, allowing readers to assess the applicability of the findings to other settings. Confirmability was addressed through reflexive practices, including the researcher's continuous reflection on potential biases and their influence on data collection and interpretation.

5.5.2 Role of the Researcher

In qualitative research, the researcher plays an active and interpretative role throughout the research process. As Tietze (2012, as cited in Saunders et al., 2016) highlights, the researcher's emotional engagement with the topic can influence the study, particularly when the subject holds personal significance. This engagement may introduce bias, both in how the data is interpreted and in the interactions with participants. In this study, the researcher remained aware of this potential and engaged

in continuous self-reflection to reduce bias and maintain transparency throughout the analysis.

As a woman researching a community centered around men's emotional experiences, the researcher also considered the potential influence of gender on the interview dynamics. There was an initial concern about whether participants would feel comfortable opening up about a male-centered space to a woman. However, the participants appeared open and reflective, and gender did not seem to restrict the depth of the conversations. Still, the researcher acknowledges that her gender may have subtly shaped what participants chose to share and how they expressed themselves. The researcher's position as an outsider may have simultaneously encouraged reflection while also introducing limits on disclosure.

5.5.3 Ethical considerations

Ethical considerations need to be made in social research, particularly during data collection, as they are closely tied to the integrity of the study and the protection of participants (Bryman, 2010). The participants of this study received the consent form presented in Appendix 4 before the interviews, presenting how their personal information would be handled. Before the start of the interviews, the participants were reminded of the objective of the research and given the opportunity to ask questions. They were also reminded that none of their personal information would be disclosed at any stage and were asked for permission to record and transcribe the interviews. To ensure anonymity, all participants were given pseudonyms, and identifying details were removed from the transcripts. The data was stored securely in a password-protected folder and was accessible only to the researcher. In accordance with data protection regulations, the audio recordings will be deleted once the research project has been completed, while the anonymized transcripts will be securely archived. Given the personal and potentially emotional nature of the conversations, participants were encouraged to share only as much as they were comfortable with and were given the option to skip questions or end the interview at any point without consequence.

6. Findings and Results

This chapter presents the key findings of the conducted interviews, organized into six thematic areas based on a reflexive thematic analysis. Each theme captures a different dimension of participants' experiences with the Conversation Clubs, including emotional responses, shifts in masculine identity, interpersonal dynamics, and perceived social impact. Themes are supported with quotes from participants to illustrate the depth and variation in their perspectives.

Most of the quotes have been translated into English and can be found in their original Finnish form in Appendix 5. To ensure transparency, these translated quotes are numbered in the text (e.g. [1]) and correspond to the full list in the appendix. Quotes from Alex, whose interview was conducted in English, appear without numbering, as no translation or appendix reference is required.

6.1 Encouraging Atmosphere

This theme explores how participants experienced the emotional and social environment of the Conversation Clubs. Many described the atmosphere as unusually open, accepting, and warm—qualities that stood in strong contrast to other environments in their lives, such as workplaces, hobbies, or male-dominated social settings. These conditions were often seen as essential for encouraging vulnerability and emotional honesty.

Several participants described a sense of being welcomed immediately, which contributed to their willingness to return.

“I noticed right away that when new guys came, they were immediately taken in very well. I sometimes have the feeling that if you go to a hobby group, they don't necessarily take the newbies into account that well. Here they immediately asked whether I was there for the first time and explained what would happen, which created the feeling that I would come again. It was this kind of warm-heartedness and it was also really easy to make friends straight away.” [1] (*Anton, l. 10*)

On the other hand, prior to attending, David questioned whether he would be emotionally “skilled” enough to participate.

“I had this image based on social media that there are just guys from Helsinki who have spent 10 years studying themselves and talking about emotions and they are so skilled that I have nothing to give. Could I even participate in the discussions, are my emotional skills at that level? All these things were going through my mind.” [2] (*David, l. 10*)

Some special formats, like Conversation Club combined with a dance class or movie night were seen as especially helpful for easing into emotional conversation:

“Luckily, I kind of chose my first Conversation Club to be one where we watched a movie and then talked about the themes of the movie. I feel that it was a really good event for first-timers, and I have said afterwards that similar events should be held and advertised, as an easy way to get involved.” [3] (*David, l. 11*)

While most participants described the atmosphere as warm, inclusive, and emotionally safe, not all felt immediately at ease.

“The first couple of times I was there, I felt a bit strange. I couldn't quite get into the dude thing. There were a bunch of the original leaders, who somehow maintain that ‘ok we talk about feelings, but we are tough guys. Maybe I haven't really found it easy to be in male groups or with males. So I had a bit of a hard time getting into it at first. Maybe it was just a kind of an initial reaction, because then I've enjoyed talking to people there.” [4] (*William, l. 10*)

Tim on the other hand felt that a shared gender identity made these events uniquely effective for emotional connection.

“Because it's all men it's easier to sort of understand other people's stories, and problems and successes. It helps the conversation in general to succeed when the way of thinking is perhaps in some way similar when you are all men and masculine people.” [5] (*Tim, l. 22*)

Others also described a sense of immediate emotional connection. Mikael talked about how he quickly felt at ease and emotionally safe in the group.

“I thought it was really cool how openly others dared and how I dared to open up myself. From that first time, I felt as if this was a group of friends that I had all along but didn’t know about. I felt so at home and secure. It was really cool that it was so open.” [6] (*Mikael, l. 21*)

This sense of openness made it easier for many participants to express themselves, even around strangers.

“There are always people there who are happy to talk about really difficult things and I find that really refreshing, even though I understand why people don't do that and especially with strangers. It's scary.” [7] (*Anton, l. 21*)

For some, this ability to connect so quickly and meaningfully—even with unfamiliar people—set the clubs apart from most everyday interactions.

“I think the interactions at these events are quite extraordinary.” [8] (*John, l. 17*)

Overall, participants experienced the atmosphere as exceptionally warm, inclusive, and supportive—conditions that many felt were crucial for allowing emotional openness and genuine connection.

6.2 Navigating Masculinity

This theme captures how participants reflect on masculinity both inside and outside the Conversation Clubs. Many spoke about the emotional limitations that men often face in everyday life, particularly in male-dominated spaces, and contrasted this with the more emotionally open model of masculinity encouraged in the clubs. Participants also shared concerns about broader societal norms around masculinity, particularly in light of growing conservative or harmful gender narratives.

Oscar acknowledged ongoing difficulties forming emotionally close friendships with other men outside of the events.

“I haven't had that many male friends and have found it difficult to form friendships with other men. [...] It could be because it is so difficult to get to know men, because it is so superficial at first and then I haven't got to the deep end as quickly as I would like to in a friendship.” [9] (*Oscar, l. 29*)

This sense of emotional distance in male friendships was echoed by others.

“I think men do have a harder time having close friend groups and places where they can be so vulnerable.” (*Alex, l. 32*)

Oliver described how competition and comparison often shape interactions between men in other environments.

“(...) among men outside these events, I think there's a small or even bigger competitiveness creeping into all those interactions. It is probably one of the cornerstones of toxic masculinity, this type of comparison and competitiveness, and it comes very often in conversations between men on some level.” [10] (*Oliver, l. 20*)

Anton felt like he did have male friends who were willing to talk openly, but haven't been given the opportunity.

“(...) the difficulty (in talking about feelings) has perhaps come in the relationships between men. In those it has felt more difficult. It doesn't mean that there haven't been men in my life who would have been quite ready to discuss such topics, but more so because we haven't been given the same opportunity.” [11] (*Anton, l. 12*)

For others, emotional distance in male friendships seemed tied to uncertainty about how much emotional openness was acceptable.

“(…) in everyday conversations with men you do not always know how much the other is willing to talk about things and how much they are willing to listen to others.” [12] (*Mikael, l. 20*)

There was also a sense of concern about the broader societal climate, particularly regarding polarization.

“It's kind of scary to see where we are as a society. Recently we were talking about physical violence and there was a representative from a youth organization in a panel discussion. They talked about how violence is still visible on the streets and how conservative values are seen a lot among young people. I can see that society is quite divided and polarized, and Jäbät ja Tunteet are on the other side of that division.” [13] (*David, l. 42*)

The influence of certain masculine role models was also a common concern.

“Originally, I was worried about the situation that I felt young men were getting themselves into, especially in the United States. With a lot of voices like Andrew Tate and Jordan Peterson, who seemed to be gaining popularity and a lot of movement. I felt that there was an unequal response to that. There wasn't many voices giving alternative ideas and places where people could get together and talk about how they're feeling and what those feelings mean and how to gain those social skills to be better individuals in the community.” (*Alex, l. 9*)

In summary, participants commonly expressed a tension between traditional masculine norms and the more open emotional culture fostered in the clubs. The clubs were seen as offering a rare and needed alternative to dominant narratives of what it means to “be a man.”

6.3 Personal Growth

This theme highlights the internal, personal transformations participants described as a result of taking part in the Conversation Clubs. These included increased emotional

awareness, improved communication and listening skills, greater confidence, and changes in how they relate to others.

For many, hearing others' stories and perspectives served as powerful turning points in how they saw themselves and their emotional patterns.

“(...) hearing someone talk about a difficulty you experience yourself and how he has overcome it, becomes an awakening experience, that oh my gosh you can also look at it from this point of view.” [14] (*Mikael, l. 13*)

Participants also noted shifts in how they perceive others, particularly other men, challenging previously held assumptions.

“My way of seeing or relating to people has changed. It has really surprised me that there are such young, street-credible, good-looking guys who are highly sensitive, open, reflective, vulnerable, and talkative. In that sense it's a broadening of the concept of men or the image of men. It's so comforting and absolutely wonderful to notice that you never really know what's good or bad about people, but perhaps above all, people can surprise you positively an awful lot.” [15] (*John, l. 22*)

For some, the clubs also helped them become more aware of their own emotional habits, and begin to develop a language to express deeper feelings.

“I've definitely been improving and working on my emotional vulnerability and ability to share my honest feelings of how I am more than just feeling tired or moody. Like what's actually behind that? And it does take some learning because it's digging into yourself and if it's something you haven't been doing, then gathering those words or trying to unpack those feelings takes effort.” (*Alex, l. 15*)

Across these accounts, participants emphasized the long-term personal growth they had experienced through repeated participation—whether in terms of emotional expression, empathy, or expanding their understanding of themselves and others.

6.4 Emotional Responses

This theme presents the emotional journey participants described before, during, and after attending the Conversation Clubs. A recurring experience was an initial sense of nervousness or hesitation—particularly during the first few sessions—which gradually gave way to feelings of comfort, relief, and even anticipation as the setting became more familiar.

Many participants recalled feeling nervous or uncertain before attending, highlighting the emotional vulnerability required to join.

“Of course the first time I was super nervous, but for a long time afterwards there was still a little bit of nerves. (...) Nowadays, or maybe the last 5, 6, 7 times, there hasn't been so much nerves anymore, but that nerves have been replaced by enthusiasm, because the event and the people are so familiar.” [16] (*David, l. 17*)

Others echoed this shift, describing how repeated participation helped build emotional safety and a sense of belonging.

“I'm not nervous anymore. But I mean, I was nervous there at first. I guess quite a few times. It might have taken me a while to relax, but now it's more natural, because I've been there so many times.” [17] (*William, l. 17*)

Some participants mentioned moments of emotional heaviness, especially when difficult topics were discussed. However, even these more intense feelings were often seen as part of a meaningful process.

“Usually after the event I have a relieved feeling and a sense of ease. But sometimes I also feel empty, so to speak. Some of these topics are a bit heavier or go deeper and if there has been something a bit harder, then the feeling might be different. I wouldn't say I feel worn out, but I feel a bit like I would after a therapy session.” [18] (*Oliver, l. 16*)

Overall, participants described a range of emotional responses tied to the clubs—starting with nervousness and growing into trust, curiosity, and connection. The emotional journey itself seemed to reflect the club’s role in helping participants step outside their comfort zones and build new emotional habits over time.

6.5 Personal Impact

Beyond internal growth, many participants described the Conversation Clubs as having a meaningful effect on their social lives and sense of connection to others. The theme of belonging and community came up frequently, particularly in relation to feeling seen, supported, and accepted.

For some, the clubs filled an important social gap, offering a space for connection they had been missing.

“I think it's been a really nice place to go and talk. It has clearly brought something good and valuable into my life. In some situations, it has felt like a really useful resource, if I've been feeling like I want to talk about something or be heard or just want to be with people in general. If I've been lonely and haven't had a lot of human contact, then this has been an easy place to go and see people and talk to people.” [19] (*William, l. 40*)

Others emphasized the value of peer support — hearing how others worked through their emotions helped them process their own.

“I think that having an in-person communal space to see how other people are working through their emotions or their day to day. And being able to open up about oneself and share, and get feedback on that and get a kind of bounce ideas back and forth is very important and very helpful.” (*Alex, l. 24*)

Anton highlighted that being actively listened to was equally important as being able to speak.

“Just the fact that everyone gets to talk and everyone is listened to has been important.” [20] (*Anton, l. 19*)

Several participants mentioned discussing topics at the Conversation Clubs that they had never talked about before.

“I remember that we had a sex-themed Conversation Club once. It was nerve-racking, but it was really valuable, because I had never had that kind of conversation before. It really stuck in my mind.” [21] (*Anton, l. 15*)

Many participants also described how these conversations introduced them to new perspectives and worldviews, which broadened their thinking and emotional understanding.

“You know, when you get to hear other people's stories around a certain topic, you always learn and see different perspectives on things.” [22] (*Mikael, l. 13*)

Overall, the Conversation Clubs had a clear impact on participants’ relationships and everyday interactions — providing a sense of connection, inspiration, and social support that many had previously lacked in other parts of their lives.

6.6 Social Impact and Influence

In addition to personal and social growth, many participants reflected on the broader significance of the Conversation Clubs. While most saw the impact as gradual and modest in scale, they believed the events contributed meaningfully to changing perceptions of masculinity in their social circles and, potentially, in society at large.

Several participants described sharing the experience with others and encouraging friends to join.

“I also realised that if you don't talk about it, others won't know about it and then the world won't go in the direction we want it to go. Of course we have to talk about it and tell people about it. I think the first thing I did was to tell my own parents. And then close relatives and friends. I've had a core group of male friends since I was in the army who I also told. In fact, one of them even joined the last Conversation Club.” [23] (*Mikael, l. 32*)

Although, not everyone felt fully comfortable disclosing their involvement.

“I’ve told a close friend that I go to these events, but not others. Some people may quickly get some preconceptions just from hearing that Jäbät ja Tunteet is the name of the community. It is somehow easier just not to advertise it very loudly.” [24] (*Oscar, l. 34*)

Tim reflected on how certain topics were valuable beyond an individual level.

“Fatherhood (was an important topic) because it's not much talked about among men. You hear a lot from women that they are asked about reproductive issues since childhood and men may be in their thirties without having ever spoken about it, since no one has asked, so it is extremely important at a social level. It is a very important thing that men should be asked sometimes.” [25] (*Tim, l. 20*)

Participants described how the clubs helped normalize emotional openness, not only within the group but also in their everyday lives.

“(…) with this openness I try to encourage others to talk and share meaningful things in everyday situations, for example at lunch at work. And when I talk about feelings, they don't always have to be difficult negative things, but could also be things that have brought you joy or happiness.” [26] (*David, l. 27*)

For some, this also meant actively challenging old norms in conversations with friends and peers.

“Many times we have also talked about, for example, how people in our own circle of friends might view masculinity. Many have even started to challenge the views of their own old groups of friends and tried to bring a bit of the Conversation Clubs' message to them.” [27] (*Oscar, l. 38*)

Others felt like it was difficult to translate the openness they had in the Conversation Clubs to friendships outside of the clubs.

“I have noticed that especially with older friendships, those that have been formed as teenagers, when talking about feelings was not present, it is more

challenging to take them towards a place where you can talk about feelings.”
[28] (*David, l. 25*)

Several participants shared the belief that small, individual changes could lead to longer-term cultural shifts, especially as more men begin to reject restrictive gender expectations.

“I think it's a significant thing for many people. Even if we can't necessarily pick the fruits of it right away, but this probably pushes quite a few men younger than myself and hopefully also those men around their twenties to paths where they know how to leave those oppressive male ideals out of their lives.” [29] (*Oliver, l. 40*)

At the same time, participants recognized the limits of the club's reach, and reflected on the difficulty of engaging those who may benefit the most.

“There is the challenge that we who go there are not necessarily the ones who need to be heard and need to share our experiences the most. We are part of the social change, but the challenge is how to involve those who maintain problematic attitudes, for example towards women or work or egocentric thinking.” [30] (*Tim, l. 38*)

Others described the club's impact as small but meaningful — a kind of “ripple effect” that could be felt on a personal level, even if not immediately visible on a larger scale.

“Yes, as much as a single small or larger thing can so yes, it is the reflection effect that comes from it. But with what weighting? I do not see a revolution in it. But I see that it can be extremely important on an individual level. Then it will be interesting to see to what extent it is visible, for example, at the stage when young guys like this who have learned to process and talk about their feelings enter a relationship? How does it begin to appear in parenting?” [31] (*John, l. 36*)

While emphasizing the positive ripple effects of attending the events John also questioned the framing of emotional growth in the community.

“The nature of the discussion in this community, or at least on Telegram, is somewhat solution-oriented. Me-centric in my opinion, which is what I find troublesome about it. For me it has echoes that focus on me and my good, where I think it is more interesting to think about how I can be better for others. But I think it's necessary for many people to get their own shit together properly first.” [32] (*John, l. 24*)

7. Discussion

The purpose of this chapter is to interpret the findings, answer the research question, and critically examine the implications in relation to the theoretical framework and existing research. The themes of encouraging atmosphere and emotional responses, as well as personal growth and personal impact, have been combined in this discussion as they offer similar insights. The rest of the themes are discussed individually, following the structure of the previous chapter.

7.1 Encouraging Atmosphere & Emotional responses

The warm, open, and accepting atmosphere described by participants formed the secure foundation of the Conversation Clubs. As emphasized, this stood in strong contrast to other male-dominated spaces in their lives. The Conversation Clubs provided an environment where openness and emotional vulnerability were not just possible, but the norm.

Participants often described the initial act of showing up as emotionally demanding. Almost all recalled feeling nervous before their first visits, and for many, this nervousness lingered over the next few sessions. As David put it, “for a long time afterwards there was still a little bit of nerves,” before this feeling was “replaced by enthusiasm.” Similarly, William reflected that “it might have taken me a while to relax, but now it’s more natural.” These reflections suggest that trust was not automatic, but developed over time. Trust being a foundation for openness is supported by the literature suggesting that trust was a key factor in disclosing sensitive topics (Gough

et al., 2021) and developing understanding of more fluid versions of masculinity (Mackenzie et al., 2017).

Repeated participation created familiarity, which made difficult emotional labor—such as discussing shame, fear, or loneliness—not only tolerable but meaningful. Oliver even compared the feeling after some events to a therapy session, underscoring the depth of emotional engagement that took place. These responses highlight how vulnerability was not the absence of discomfort, but a process that involved risk, reflection, and emotional growth over time.

A critical element in this process appeared to be the male-only setting. Tim noted that “because it’s all men... the way of thinking is perhaps in some way similar,” which made deeper conversations easier. This aligns with Milligan et al.’s (2013) suggestion that homosocial environments provide men with a cultural “permission structure” to engage in emotional expression—one that might not be available in mixed-gender settings. While such spaces can reproduce certain masculine norms, they can also function as sites where new emotional practices are rehearsed and normalized, allowing for new forms of masculinity to occur (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005; Lomas, 2013).

The ability to open up emotionally was repeatedly described as a surprising and meaningful experience by participants. Mikael, for instance, reflected on how quickly a sense of trust emerged, while Anton noted how rare and “refreshing” it was to engage in open conversations, even with strangers, despite the fear it could evoke. This atmosphere of safety and connection helped normalize emotional vulnerability—something John described as “extraordinary.” These reflections echo findings from Addis (2011), Lomas (2013), and McQueen (2017), who all emphasize that men are willing to express emotions when provided with the right environments.

That said, not everyone felt at home immediately. William’s experience illustrates the uncertainty some felt toward male-only vulnerability. He described early discomfort with “the dude thing,” perceiving that some of the original organizers performed a blend of emotional openness and traditional toughness. This tension reflects what

McQueen (2017) describes as the dual pressures men face between the competing discourses of “boys don’t cry” and “it’s good to talk.”

Another barrier some faced was a perception that emotional competence was a prerequisite for participation. David, worried about whether his “emotional skills were at that level,” reflected an unintended pressure that even well-intentioned spaces can generate. This suggests that while openness is the norm within the club, the threshold for entry may still feel high for newcomers—especially those unfamiliar with emotional talk. To address this, some participants recommended alternative entry points, such as events built around shared activities (e.g., a movie night or sports class), which provided a lower-stakes way to participate. These formats, as David noted, helped ease him into the space by creating initial comfort before shifting into emotional discussion.

In sum, the Conversation Clubs were described as uniquely safe, emotionally supportive spaces—but safety did not mean immediate ease for everyone. It was built over time, through shared norms, repeated contact, and mutual vulnerability. Trust, repetition, and a clearly communicated ethos were key to enabling the kind of openness participants described. The male-only context helped reduce social pressure, and small structural choices—like how first-timers were welcomed or how events were themed—played a large role in lowering barriers. Importantly, the study also reveals how even safe spaces can produce new forms of pressure, such as the expectation of being emotionally “skilled.” This highlights the need for thoughtful design when creating inclusive environments, especially those seeking to challenge traditional norms of masculinity.

These findings also confirm the assumptions outlined in the methodology. One core assumption was that men often struggle with emotional vulnerability, particularly in male-only groups, and that emotional suppression is not innate but socially conditioned. The evidence from participants supports this view: initial nervousness, gradual trust-building, and developing emotional competence all reflect how masculinity and emotional expression are shaped by the environment. Another assumption was that peer-based, non-judgmental environments could help shift

emotional norms. The findings strongly affirm this, showing that emotional expression became normalized through shared participation, suggesting the effectiveness of intentional social design in facilitating healthier models of masculinity.

7.2 Navigating Masculinity

The findings showed that many participants thought deeply about masculinity both inside and outside the Conversation Clubs. Several described how everyday male spaces—such as workplaces, hobbies, and social groups—often made it difficult to talk about feelings. Competition, comparison, and keeping conversations light were seen as common features in those settings. In contrast, the Conversation Clubs offered a different model of being a man, where emotional openness and reflection were not just allowed but encouraged.

The reflections on difficulties to form meaningful friendships with other men outside of the Conversations Clubs is supported by Richardson & Smith (2011) who state that men have a harder time forming deep friendships than women. Oliver's comment about competitiveness creeping into conversations between men highlights how certain forms of masculinity are still closely tied to comparison and status. This observation is supported by research that links traditional masculine norms to emotional restraint and social competition (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005; Kimmel, 1994). It also shows why spaces like the Conversation Clubs feel so different — because they challenge those norms rather than reinforce them.

Anton spoke about how he did have men in his life who were willing to talk about emotions, but that they had not been given the opportunity, echoed by Mikeal who felt some hesitation regarding how much others were willing to share and listen. These findings correlate with Gough et al. (2021) emphasizing that men do talk about feelings, but others might not be listening or encouraging those behaviors.

From the perspective of CPM, the clubs can be seen as creating alternative models of masculinity that are healthier and more diverse (Lomas, 2013). CPM highlights the importance of building positive masculine identities that are not based on dominance

or emotional suppression, but on connection, reflection, and care. Many participants in this study seemed to embrace these new models.

Participants were highly aware of contradicting societal trends—mentioning the rise of conservative values, violence, and harmful male role models. This shows that the clubs offer an important counterspace, while the work of reshaping masculinity at a societal level remains ongoing and complex. Several participants contrasted their experiences at the clubs with male-focused online movements that promote harmful or regressive views. These comparisons to outgroups—often referencing influencers or ideologies that endorse emotional suppression or dominance—served to reinforce participants’ identification with the values of *Jäbät ja Tunteet*. In line with SIT (Tajfel & Turner, 1979), this sense of contrast strengthened their group cohesion and deepened their commitment to the club’s ethos of openness, respect, and emotional reflection.

Moreover, participants’ reflections often implicitly engaged with the public discourse on toxic versus healthy masculinity. By rejecting emotionally restrictive norms and embracing vulnerability, participants positioned themselves in opposition to stereotypical “toxic” models. This not only highlights the transformative potential of the clubs but also shows how the movement resonates within broader cultural debates around gender and emotional well-being.

7.3 Personal Growth and Impact

The Conversation Clubs fostered not only personal development but also a broader impact on participants’ lives. On a personal level, many described becoming better at identifying, expressing, and processing emotions. These skills were not innate but developed over time through practice, reflection, and exposure to others’ emotional journeys. As Alex noted, learning to uncover those hidden feelings takes practice, and “having an in-person communal space to see how other people are working through their emotions... is very important and very helpful.” This underscores Holmes’ (2015) point that emotional expression is a skill that improves with repeated use and supportive feedback.

The participants' experiences align closely with what CPM encourages: the building of positive, flexible masculine identities that allow emotional vulnerability (Lomas, 2013). Being able to listen, to reflect, and to share emotions are important parts of this. As Mikael described, hearing others' stories often acted as a trigger for personal insights and emotional development. These moments of realization suggest that emotional learning happens not only through personal reflection but also socially—through exposure to different ways of seeing and handling emotions.

At the same time, the social environment was equally transformative. Being part of a group where emotional openness was normalized allowed participants to engage vulnerably without fear of judgment. SIT (Tajfel & Turner, 1979) helps explain this: the shared identity of the group reduced social risk and increased conformity to group norms—in this case, empathy, openness, and listening. For many, the clubs provided a sense of belonging and support that had been missing elsewhere. William shared that the events became a valued resource, especially during times of loneliness: “If I’ve been lonely... this has been an easy place to go and see people and talk to people.”

These peer-based conversations also encouraged participants to expand their emotional and social awareness. Several described how hearing others' stories introduced them to new ways of thinking. As Mikael put it, “you always learn and see different perspectives on things.” Talking about previously unspoken topics—like Anton’s experience with a sex-themed event—challenged personal boundaries in ways that promoted both growth and connection. Noticing how even “street credible” men belonged to this group reshaped John’s way of relating to others, challenging assumptions about who is allowed to show vulnerability.

In short, emotional growth and personal impact were deeply intertwined. The clubs helped participants build confidence, emotional competence, and empathy—while also filling a social gap through community, belonging, and peer validation. This mirrors the aims of CPM (Lomas, 2013), which encourages new, healthier models of masculinity grounded in openness, care, and connection. These patterns of emotional development further reflect Jäbät ja Tunteet’s broader role as a grassroots social movement. By creating emotionally safe environments where men are encouraged to

practice vulnerability and self-awareness, the initiative contributes to reshaping emotional norms from the bottom up.

7.4 Social Impact and Influence

The final theme highlights how the Conversation Clubs not only supported individual development but also acted as catalysts for broader social influence. Participants described how the practices of emotional openness, active listening, and reflection they learned in the clubs often extended beyond the event itself. These behaviors were carried into everyday interactions—with friends, colleagues, and family members—shaping how participants communicated and related to others. Sometimes this influence was subtle, simply by modeling a different way of being; other times, it involved actively encouraging others to engage in deeper, more emotionally honest conversations.

This reflects what the participants often called the “ripple effect”: small changes at the personal level radiating outward into wider social networks. As Tim noted, some of the conversations—such as those around fatherhood—were not only personally meaningful but socially significant. His reflection illustrates how topics explored in the clubs often carried cultural and generational relevance, tapping into broader social shifts in how masculinity and care are understood.

This echoes one of the core ideas of CPM: that the transformation of masculine norms is most effective not through grand, revolutionary gestures, but through small, everyday practices (Lomas, 2013). By engaging in open, vulnerable dialogue, participants were challenging inherited masculine scripts—and in doing so, they became informal agents of cultural change. This micro-level influence aligns closely with the concept of grassroots activism: rather than aiming for systemic reform through traditional channels, the change occurs interpersonally and relationally. As these new emotional norms spread through conversation and example, the potential for wider cultural impact increases.

In this way, the participants’ actions reflect Jäbät ja Tunteet’s function as a social movement. While Jäbät ja Tunteet meets the structural characteristics of a social

movement as outlined by Tilly and Tarrow (2007), its deeper impact is best understood through Melucci's (1996) concept of "movements of meaning," where transformation occurs not just through formal claims but through the redefinition of everyday practices and emotional norms. The clubs may not organize protests or publish manifestos, but they represent a cultural movement aiming to reshape emotional life and gender expectations from within. Their approach embodies Melucci's (1996) notion of "movements of meaning," which challenge dominant ideologies by cultivating new identities, symbols, and forms of practice in everyday life. The peer-led, voluntary nature of the initiative underscores its grassroots character: transformation happens through collective reflection and community-building, not institutional mandate.

However, this spread was not without resistance or complication. While many participants described becoming more emotionally expressive in their wider lives, others acknowledged barriers. Oscar, for instance, shared that he was hesitant to tell others about attending a group centered on male emotionality, due to lingering stigma. This reflects Connell's (1995) argument that hegemonic masculinity continues to police emotional expression, especially among men, even as new models emerge. David similarly noted the difficulty of bringing new emotional habits into older friendships, where vulnerability was never part of the dynamic. This is supported by research on Men's Shed, which found that emotional practices may be difficult to carry into everyday life beyond the group (Wilson & Cordier, 2013; Golding, 2015). These examples underscore the ongoing tension between individual change and broader social structures.

Another critical reflection came from John, who questioned the sometimes "me-centric" tone of the discussions. He felt that while self-reflection was valuable, it could occasionally come at the expense of collective or outward-facing awareness. His perspective draws attention to the challenge of balancing personal growth with a more community-oriented ethos—a challenge echoed in broader critiques of therapeutic cultures (Illouz, 2008). It suggests that for these spaces to catalyze truly transformative social change, they may also need to nurture a shared sense of responsibility and relational awareness.

Finally, while many participants spoke enthusiastically about their personal growth, they also made the important note that those who joined the clubs were already, to some extent, open to change. As such, these spaces may not yet be reaching the men who are most deeply entrenched in restrictive emotional norms. This aligns with research on emotional socialization, which shows that traditional masculine norms still inhibit many men from seeking help or expressing vulnerability (Addis & Mahalik, 2003). Expanding the accessibility and appeal of such spaces remains a critical task.

In sum, the Conversation Clubs represent a modest but meaningful site of cultural transformation. Through everyday acts of emotional openness and shared reflection, participants are not only reshaping their own identities but also contributing to a broader movement that challenges and redefines masculinity in Finnish society. While challenges remain—including stigma, accessibility, and the balance between self-focus and collective orientation—the findings demonstrate how small, peer-led initiatives can serve as powerful vehicles for social change.

7.5 Answering the Research Question

The central aim of this study was to explore both the individual and societal benefits of the Conversation Clubs hosted by Jäbät ja Tunteet. To address this, the research question posed was:

RQ: What are the individual and societal benefits of events by Jäbät ja Tunteet?

The findings of this study demonstrate that the Conversation Clubs offer meaningful individual benefits, particularly in fostering emotional openness, reflection, and personal growth. Participants described how the clubs helped them explore their emotions more deeply, challenge internalized masculine norms, and develop a stronger sense of emotional literacy. Many noted that these experiences were both rare and valuable in their everyday lives, suggesting the events filled a gap in traditional masculine socialization. The clubs functioned as psychologically safe spaces where emotional vulnerability was not only permitted but encouraged, helping participants cultivate more flexible and supportive models of masculinity.

In terms of personal impact, participants also spoke to the value of connection, belonging, and peer support. Hearing others' emotional stories often led to new insights and greater empathy, supporting the idea that emotional development can happen socially, not just through introspection. For some, simply being listened to—or witnessing other men express vulnerability—was a transformative experience. These outcomes reflect the goals of CPM, which emphasizes the importance of emotional expression, relational awareness, and community in reshaping male identity (Lomas, 2013).

Beyond the individual level, the research also uncovered important societal benefits. Many participants described how the emotional practices and relational models developed in the clubs extended into their broader social networks. They spoke of “ripple effects”—where shifts in their own emotional openness subtly influenced friends, partners, and family members. This supports the notion that cultural change often begins in micro-settings, through repeated, everyday behaviors and interactions. Conversations on topics like fatherhood, violence, or misogyny were seen not just as personal, but as socially and politically relevant.

Participants' comparisons to more harmful masculinity movements also underscored their sense of identification with Jäbät ja Tunteet's values. This contrast strengthened group cohesion and exemplifies a core dynamic of SIT (Tajfel & Turner, 1979), where belonging is reinforced through differentiation from outgroups. Additionally, many participants' reflections resonated with the public discourse on toxic versus healthy masculinity. Their emphasis on emotional openness, vulnerability, and care reveals how they were not only engaging in personal growth, but also contributing to a wider cultural reimagining of what it means to be a man.

These findings also affirm the assumptions outlined in the methodology. Men in this study did report emotional struggles rooted in social expectations, but they also showed that these barriers could be overcome in a supportive peer environment. The clubs enabled new forms of expression and community, demonstrating that emotional suppression is not inherent but contextually reinforced—and thus, possible to change.

While the scale of impact may be modest, the study ultimately shows that Jäbät ja Tunteet functions both as a personal development initiative and as a grassroots social movement. By combining safe emotional practice with cultural critique, the Conversation Clubs represent a powerful, community-based model for challenging hegemonic masculinity and advancing healthier norms of emotional life. The findings indicate that even informal, peer-led spaces can produce meaningful individual change while contributing to broader cultural transformation.

8. Conclusion

This study set out to explore the individual and societal benefits of the Conversation Clubs organized by Jäbät ja Tunteet. Drawing on qualitative interviews with nine participants, the research found that these events foster emotional growth, build community, and challenge dominant norms of masculinity. Participants described increased emotional awareness, personal development, and a newfound sense of belonging. These benefits extended beyond the events themselves, influencing relationships and communication patterns in everyday life. Taken together, the findings suggest that Jäbät ja Tunteet operates not only as a peer support space but also as a grassroots cultural movement redefining what it means to be a man in contemporary Finnish society.

The results affirm that emotional suppression is socially conditioned rather than inherent, and that supportive, peer-based environments can shift how men relate to their emotions and to each other. Drawing from Masculinity Theory, CPM and SIT, the study reveals how community, trust, and shared values enable new emotional norms to emerge and spread. The clubs provided participants with a counter-narrative to dominant masculinity discourses, and a practical site for enacting emotional openness.

8.1 Scientific and Practical Relevance

This study contributes to the field of culture and event management by highlighting how informal, community-driven events can serve as powerful tools for social change.

Rather than relying on institutional intervention, initiatives like Jäbät ja Tunteet illustrate how cultural norms can shift from the ground up—through conversation, ritual, and repetition. These findings have implications not only for gender studies and peer support practices, but also for how we design, facilitate, and evaluate events intended to foster social impact.

From a practical perspective, the results offer valuable insights for organizers, facilitators, and policymakers interested in creating safe and transformative spaces for emotional expression. The findings suggest that structure, repetition, and peer-based facilitation are key components in fostering openness and emotional growth. This research may also inform the development of similar grassroots initiatives, both in Finland and internationally, seeking to challenge restrictive gender norms and improve community well-being.

8.2 Limitations

This research is subject to several limitations that should be acknowledged. The sample was limited to individuals who had attended at least five Conversation Clubs and were willing to participate in an interview. This means the findings reflect the experiences of men already engaged with the community and open to discussing emotional topics. Those who are less comfortable with such discussions or who did not continue attending were not represented, potentially limiting the diversity of perspectives. Furthermore, while the coding process produced a range of interesting insights, not all codes could be discussed within the scope of this thesis. Nevertheless, these codes were included in the codebook to ensure transparency and to reflect the broader richness of the data. It is also worth noting that the societal impacts identified in the findings are partly speculative due to the inherently subjective nature of qualitative research. Finally, the study is grounded in a specific geographical and cultural context which may influence the nature of emotional expression, masculinity norms, and community engagement. As such, while the findings offer valuable insights, they might not be directly transferable to similar initiatives in other cultural settings.

8.3 Recommendations for Future Research

Future research could examine how to design similar spaces for men from diverse cultural or socioeconomic backgrounds. It would also be valuable to explore strategies for reaching men who might benefit from peer-support communities like Jäbät ja Tunteet but may not initially be open to participating.

Additionally, further studies could investigate how the core principles of Jäbät ja Tunteet might be adapted to other event formats — such as festivals, workplaces, or educational institutions — and what barriers may arise when translating these models into different contexts. Given that Jäbät ja Tunteet has also organized events open to all genders, future research could also explore how such cross-gender dialogue forums shape participant experiences and affect emotional expression.

Finally, comparative studies involving similar international initiatives, such as Men's Shed or Andy's Man Club, could offer a broader perspective on how masculinity is being renegotiated across different cultural settings.

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Appendix

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Appendix 1 - Interview guide (EN)

Part 1: introduction

Thank you for participating in my study. I am interested in your personal experiences related to the community and particularly the Conversation Clubs. I want to remind you that this conversation is strictly confidential and no personal details will be published. You can share as much as you are comfortable with and if there is a question you do not want to answer that is okay. Do you have any questions before we start? Do you give your consent for me to transcribe this interview?

-Can you tell me about how and when you first heard of Jäbät ja Tunteet?

-Approximately how many Conversation Clubs have you attended? In which city did you attend?

-What drew you to the community?

-What made you go to a Conversation Club in the first place? Has the reason you go changed over time? How was the first time?

-Has it always been natural for you to speak about your feelings, or did you feel discouraged to do so prior to finding the community?

Part 2: Focus on the events

- How do you generally feel before and after a Conversation Club?

-Has there been some specific topics that have been especially important for you to discuss?

-How would you describe the environment in these events? Is the interaction different to that you have experienced among men outside these events?

Part 3: Personal impact

-Have these discussions influenced how you communicate in your daily life?

-Do you feel you've changed personally because of these events? In what ways?

-Have you noticed any change in how you process your emotions?

Part 4: Influence on others

-Have you shared something from these events with friends or family?

-Have you encouraged others to join or talk more openly about their emotions? If so, are you limiting it to close friends, or do you advocate for the community more broadly, for example on social media?

-What kind of reactions do you get when you bring these topics up outside the community?

Part 5: Societal and cultural reflections

-Do you see Jäbät ja Tunteet as part of a bigger cultural shift?

-What role do you think these events play in changing societal views on masculinity?

-Is there something more the community could do to create social change?

Part 6: Wrapping up

- If you had to describe what Jäbät ja Tunteet means to you, how would you put it?

-These were all my questions, but what should I have asked that I didn't give you an opportunity to share?

Thank you for participating in my study, I greatly appreciate it. If you want I can share my thesis with you once it is done.

Appendix 2 - Interview guide (FI)

Osa 1: Esittely

Tässä haastattelussa käsitellään sinun henkilökohtaisia kokemuksia liittyen Jäbät ja Tunteet yhteisöön, ja etenkin Conversation Clubeihin. Muistutan että haastattelu on täysin anonyymi, eikä sinun henkilökohtaisia tietoja jaeta missään vaiheessa. Voit jakaa sen verran, kun tuntuu hyvältä, ja jos et halua vastata johonkin kysymykseen niin se on täysin ok. Onko sulla kysymyksiä ennen, kun aloitetaan? Annatko suostumuksesi tämän haastattelun transkribointiin?

-Voisitko aluksi kertoa milloin ja miten kuulit Jäbät & Tunteet yhteisöstä ensimmäistä kertaa?

-Osaatko sanoa suunnilleen, miten moneen Conversation Clubiin olet osallistunut? Missä kaupungissa olet osallistunut?

-Mikä yhteisössä veti puoleensa?

-Mikä sai sinut menemään Conversation Club ensimmäistä kertaa? Onko syy, miksi menet edelleen sama vai onko motiivisi muuttunut ajan myötä?

-Onko tunteista puhuminen ollut sinulle aina luontevaa, vai oletko tuntenut, että et voi puhua niistä vapaasti ennen, kun löysit Jäbät & Tunteet?

Osa 2: Tapahtumat

-Millainen fiilis sinulla on ennen ja jälkeen Conversation Clubin?

-Onko sinulle ollut erityisen tärkeää päästä puhumaan jostain tietystä aiheesta?

-Miten kuvailisit tapahtumien ilmapiiriä? Onko vuorovaikutus erilainen, kun mitä olet kokenut miesten välillä tapahtumien ulkopuolella?

Osa 3: Henkilökohtainen vaikutus

-Onko tapahtumissa käydyillä keskusteluilla ollut vaikutus siihen, miten kommunikoit arjessa?

-Koetko että olet muuttunut tapahtumien myötä? Miten?

-Oletko huomannut muutoksia siinä, miten käsittelet tunteitasi?

Osa 4: Vaikutus muihin

-Oletko jakanut kokemuksia tapahtumista perheesi tai ystävien kanssa?

-Oletko kannustanut muita osallistumaan tapahtumiin tai puhumaan tunteistaan avoimemmin? Jos kyllä, oletko rajoittanut sen läheisiin ystäviin, vai puhutko yhteisön/sen teemojen puolesta laajemmin, esimerkiksi somessa?

-Minkälaisia reaktioita olet saanut, jos olet puhunut näistä aiheista yhteisön ulkopuolella?

Osa 5: Yhteiskunnalliset ja sosiaaliset vaikutukset

-Koetko että Jäbät ja Tunteet ovat osa suurempaa kulttuurista muutosta?

-Koetko että nämä tapahtumat voivat muuttaa yhteiskunnallista käsitystä maskuliinisuudesta?

-Onko jotain mitä yhteisö voisi tehdä vaikuttaakseen yhteiskunnalliseen muutokseen, jota he eivät vielä tee?

Osa 6: Lopetellaan

-Mitä Jäbät ja Tunteet merkitsee sinulle?

-Mun kysymykset alkavat olemaan tässä, mutta mitä minun olisi pitänyt kysyä, mitä et vielä päässyt jakamaan?

Kiitos osallistumisesta, arvostan sitä suuresti! Jos haluat voin jakaa gradun kanssasi, kun se on valmis.

Appendix 3 – Codebook

Theme: Atmosphere

Code	Description	Example Quote
Welcoming	Describes how the participants feel welcome and how newcomers are considered.	“(…) the way the Conversation Clubs have been set up has been very inviting and I've had several friends who I've brought to check it out and all of them have felt that it is a very inviting and welcoming place.” <i>(Alex, l. 15)</i>
Secure Setting	Refers to how the setting allows for emotional openness and creates a feeling of safety. Also used when participants say that they trust what they share will stay within the group.	“I think it's an unimaginable difference when men talk to each other outside a Conversation Club versus there, where you know that you can and should talk as openly as you want and can. We are aware that we are all in some way on the same page. Everyone is ready to talk about their feelings and everyone is open about it, so there is perhaps a bit more freedom to talk.” <i>(Mikael, l. 20)</i>
Encouraging Presence	Captures how the structure or environment encourages participants to be fully present—minimizing distractions and fostering deep listening and connection in the moment.	“Every single time after the Conversation Club, I've said, being really present for a couple of hours, talking and listening to other people's thoughts and experiences and sharing your own without using a phone, it makes you feel really grounded and calm.” <i>(David, l. 17)</i>

Relaxed	Captures how participants experience the atmosphere as easygoing, informal, and without pressure. This includes feeling that nothing is forced.	“I think it's very (...) relaxed. I've heard the same from first-time visitors, that it's somehow just a really relaxed atmosphere, that it's not like anything is forced.” <i>(Anton, l. 21)</i>
Accepting	Describes how the atmosphere encourages everyone to be themselves and accept others as they are. There is no need to be a certain way.	“The atmosphere of the discussions is so very accepting and so calm.” <i>(Tim, l. 22)</i>
Warm	Describes how participants experience the space as emotionally warm and friendly. This goes beyond feeling “relaxed” and includes a sense of emotional care, kindness, and connection.	“In Conversation Clubs it's really kind of a warm and friendly atmosphere.” <i>(David, l. 22)</i>
Courageous	Used when participants describe how the setting allows emotional bravery—either in themselves or in others. Includes elements of surprise over how much one <i>dares</i> to share with strangers.	“I thought it was really cool how openly others dared and how I dared to open up myself. From that first time, I felt as if this was a group of friends that I had all along but didn't know about. I felt so at home and secure. It was really cool that it was so open.” <i>(Mikael, l. 21)</i>

Theme: Navigating Masculinity

Code	Description	Example Quote
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Surface-Level Interactions	Captures how most conversations between men (at work, hobbies, or among casual friends) tend to stay superficial, making it hard to transition into deeper emotional topics.	“I study in a very male dominated field, and there at least I find that if you meet new men the conversation can be very superficial. There may also be some male friends you've known for several months, and rarely do those friendships lead to a proper conversation about feelings or anything else. It's surprisingly difficult to get to that point.” (<i>Oscar, l. 24</i>)
Emotional Hesitation and Limits	Reflects the internal or social barriers that make it difficult to open up emotionally with other men — including hesitation, fear of judgment, or not knowing how others will respond.	“Maybe I have missed it on a certain level, that many of those topics can't really be talked about in the same way outside the events. Or you could talk about them, but the structure of the conversation is just different. You can't dictate if you see a group of friends and say, well, now we're talking about shame.” (<i>Anton, l. 21</i>)
Shifting Friendships and Emotional Space	Explores how emotional conversations are easier in specific contexts (e.g., one-on-one or in the Conversation Club) and how older friendships can be harder to shift into new emotional territory.	“I have noticed that especially with older friendships, those that have been formed as teenagers, when talking about feelings was not present, it is more challenging to take them towards a place where you can talk about feelings.” (<i>David, l. 21</i>)
State of the world	Captures participants' reflections on broader societal trends, concerns, or cultural shifts—often expressed through worry or critique. This includes comments	“It's kind of scary to see where we are as a society. Recently we were talking about physical violence and there was a representative from a youth organisation in a panel discussion. They talked about

	<p>on the influence of public figures, the political or emotional climate among men, generational divides, and the lack of emotional or communal spaces in society. The tone is typically outward-looking, focusing on what is happening in the world and how it shapes or limits emotional growth and connection.</p>	<p>how violence is still visible on the streets and how conservative values are seen a lot among young people. I can see that society is quite divided and polarised, and Jäbät ja Tunteet are on the other side of that division.” (<i>David, l. 42</i>)</p>
Emotional Norms	<p>Captures participants’ reflections on the societal expectations and unspoken rules around emotional expression, particularly among men. This includes observations about how men are often discouraged from showing vulnerability or talking about feelings, as well as the stigma or discomfort that can arise when these norms are challenged. The code encompasses both personal experiences with these pressures and broader cultural commentary about what emotions are “acceptable” for men to express and where.</p>	<p>“I like to mention it and even a bit annoyingly always bring this up, because the assumption among men is still pretty much to stay quieter about things like this.” (<i>Tim, l. 32</i>)</p>
Masculinity Models	<p>Refers to participants’ reflections on different versions of masculinity they have encountered, rejected, or are</p>	<p>“(…) among men outside events, I think there's a small or even bigger competitiveness creeping into all those interactions. It is probably one of the</p>

	<p>trying to embody. This includes critiques of traditional or "toxic" masculinity, observations about shifting ideals, and discussions about the kinds of male role models present in society. The code also captures how participants compare dominant cultural models—such as being stoic, competitive, or emotionally distant—with alternative, more emotionally open and vulnerable expressions of manhood.</p>	<p>cornerstones of toxic masculinity, this type of comparison and competitiveness, and it comes very often in conversations between men on some level.” (<i>Oliver, l. 20</i>)</p>
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Theme: Personal Growth

Code	Description	Example Quote
Confidence	<p>A growing sense of self-assurance which can include belief in one's abilities, comfort in expressing personal opinions, or feeling more at ease being oneself in social and emotional contexts.</p>	<p>“I have gained more confidence from these events. Or just somehow the confidence to be more myself and say what I think. I have also gained courage to express myself.” (<i>William, l. 25</i>)</p>
Communication Skills	<p>Improvement in expressing thoughts, holding meaningful conversations and emotional articulation.</p>	<p>“I have learned to articulate my thoughts and feelings much better” (<i>David, l. 13</i>)</p>
Listening Skills	<p>Refers to the development of deeper listening abilities, such as being fully present, not</p>	<p>“I am much more skilful and can also take others into account much more easily, and I don't feel that I have to have the last word</p>

	interrupting, and accepting others' perspectives without rushing to respond or fix.	or give people some good advice. Sometimes you can just let things go and listen to what the other person wants to say.” (<i>Tim, l. 26</i>)
Emotional Processing	Describes an increased capacity to understand, manage, and express emotions in healthier ways.	“Yes, the knowledge that there is a place to talk and vent is a relief in itself. Easily if there is no established place or group of friends or partner to talk to, you can bottle up your own feelings inside for a very long time. So visiting Conversation Clubs and talking has helped in dealing with emotions.” (<i>Oscar, l. 31</i>)
Transformative Realizations	Refers to moments of insight or “aha” experiences where participants come to understand themselves, others, or masculinity in new ways. Often triggered by hearing someone else's story or perspective.	“(…) hearing someone talk about a difficulty you experience yourself and how he has overcome it, becomes an awakening experience, that oh my gosh you can also look it from this point of view.” (<i>Mikael, l. 13</i>)
Relating to Others	Describes changes in how participants perceive or connect with other people, particularly other men. Includes increased empathy, openness to difference, or shifts in assumptions and expectations.	“Yeah my way of seeing or relating to people has changed. It has really surprised me that there are such young, street-credible, good-looking guys who are highly sensitive, open, reflective, vulnerable, and talkative. So in that sense it's a broadening of the concept of men or the image of men. Yes, it's so comforting and it's absolutely wonderful to somehow

		notice that you never really know what's good or bad about people, but perhaps above all, people can surprise you positively an awful lot." (<i>John, l. 22</i>)
Opening up Emotionally	Captures participants' growing ability to access, name, and share their feelings. This includes practicing emotional vulnerability and moving beyond surface-level expressions to explore what's beneath.	"I've definitely been improving and working on my emotional vulnerability and ability to share my honest feelings of how I am more than just feeling tired or moody. Like what's actually behind that? And it does take some learning because it's digging into yourself and if it's something you haven't been doing, then gathering those words or trying to unpack those feelings that you're having." (<i>Alex, l. 15</i>)

Theme: Emotional Responses

Code	Description	Example Quote
Nervousness	Describes the anxiety or unease participants felt, particularly when attending their first Conversation Club, and how these feelings might persist in subsequent events. This nervousness often stems from the vulnerability required in sharing personal thoughts and emotions.	"(...) there's a little bit of tension and shyness at the beginning of these events, so it can be a bit difficult to be vulnerable and to throw yourself into the subject." (<i>Oliver, l. 20</i>)
Feeling good	Refers to the positive emotional response participants experience as a result of attending the events.	"The first conversation left me with a good feeling." (<i>Oscar, l. 13</i>)

	This sense of well-being often comes after the event, where they feel fulfilled, content, or uplifted.	
Enthusiasm	Reflects the growing excitement and eagerness participants feel as they anticipate future events. This enthusiasm often increases over time as participants become more comfortable and connected to the group.	“Nowadays, I'm not necessarily nervous anymore, and I'm more looking forward to getting there.” (<i>John, l. 13</i>)
Comfort	Describes the sense of emotional safety and ease that participants feel when they're part of the group, where mutual interest and support help them relax and open up. This feeling of comfort often arises from being in an environment where vulnerability is accepted and encouraged, as well as noticing others have similar struggles to yours.	“(…) it was really comforting to have a group like that, who was interested to share their own experiences and hear others.” (<i>Alex, l. 11</i>)
Relief/Ease	Refers to the emotional release participants experience after attending the events, often characterized by a sense of relief or lightness. However, it can sometimes coexist with moments of emotional heaviness,	“Usually after it is a relieved feeling and a sense of ease. But then sometimes I also feel empty, so to speak. Some of these topics are a bit heavier or we have gone a bit deeper and if there has been something a bit harder, then it is of course a bit more difficult. I still wouldn't say I feel worn

	particularly after more intense or deeply personal conversations.	out, but I feel a bit like I would after a therapy session.” (<i>Oliver, l. 16</i>)
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Theme: Personal Impact

Code	Description	Example Quote
Belonging	Captures the feeling of being part of a meaningful group or community. Often refers to experiences of connection, rootedness, or having “a place.”	“And a sense of community, of feeling part of something for the first time really since I’ve living here in the Capital Region.” (<i>Tim, l. 44</i>)
Support	Refers to the emotional, conversational, and social support received from the group. Includes feeling heard, validated, encouraged, or helped by others through shared reflections, feedback, and similar experiences.	“I think that having an in-person communal space to see how other people are working through their emotions or their day to day. And being able to open up about oneself and share, and get feedback on that and get a kind of bounce ideas back and forth is very important and very helpful.” (<i>Alex, l. 24</i>)
Likeminded People	Describes the experience of finding others who share similar values, emotional depth, or outlook on life. Often linked to ease in forming genuine friendships and a sense of resonance with others.	“I haven't had that many male friends and have found it difficult to form friendships with other men. Now in the last 5 years I have felt that I have not found men around me who are on the same wavelength. It could be because it is so difficult to get to know men, because it is so superficial at first and then I haven't got to the deep end as quickly as I would like to in a friendship. But then when I've been to the

		Conversation Clubs, I've realised that there are a lot of guys like me and maybe I've been in circles where they weren't so open." (<i>Oscar, l. 29</i>)
Inspiring People	Captures moments where participants felt uplifted, inspired, or positively influenced by the insights or intelligence, of others in the group.	"Someone might have said something really clever and then I've got this nice feeling of being surrounded by really clever people." (<i>Anton, l. 19</i>)
New Conversations	Refers to engaging in topics that participants had not previously discussed, or reaching a level of depth and vulnerability that felt new and significant.	"I haven't really experienced anything like that in my life, to get into this kind of discussion about something." (<i>William, l. 11</i>)
Perspective	Highlights how exposure to diverse stories and viewpoints in the group has broadened participants' understanding of others, themselves, or the world.	"You know, when you get to hear other people's stories around a certain topic, you always learn and see different perspectives on things." (<i>Mikeal, l. 13</i>)
Social Life	Describes how the group has positively contributed to participants' social routines, offering meaningful human interaction, especially in times of loneliness or reduced connection.	"I think it's been a really nice place to go and talk. It has clearly brought something good and valuable into my life. In some situations it has felt like a really useful resource, if I've been feeling like I want to talk about something or be heard or just want to be with people in general. If I've been lonely and haven't had a lot of human contact, then this has been a really easy

		place to go and see people and talk to people.” (<i>William, l. 40</i>)
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Theme: Social Impact and Influence

Code	Description	Example Quote
Societal Change	Refers to the long-term or larger societal shifts that participants perceive as a result of the events. This might include changes in the perception of masculinity, emotional expression, or the broader role of men in society.	“I think it's a significant thing for many people. Even if we can't necessarily pick the fruits of it right away, but this probably pushes quite a few men younger than myself and hopefully also those men around their twenties to paths where they know how to leave those oppressive male ideals out of their lives.” (<i>Oliver, l. 40</i>)
Challenging Norms	Describes how participants recognize the events' role in encouraging individuals, especially men, to question and break away from traditional, rigid societal norms around masculinity. This code captures moments where individuals challenge outdated expectations or norms in their personal circles, helping reshape gender norms.	“Many times we have also talked about, for example, how people in our own circle of friends might view masculinity and masculinity. Many have even started to challenge the views of their own old groups of friends and tried to bring a bit of the Conversation Clubs' message to them.” (<i>Oscar, l. 38</i>)
Peer-to-peer Influence	Reflects how participants share and encourage the emotional openness and learning they have gained from the events with peers,	“(…) with this openness I try to encourage others to talk and share meaningful things in everyday situations, for example at lunch at work. And when I talk about

	<p>particularly in informal, everyday settings. This code captures the interpersonal, peer-driven impact that extends the influence beyond the events themselves.</p>	<p>feelings, they don't always have to be difficult negative things, but could also be things that have brought you joy or happiness.” (<i>David, l. 27</i>)</p>
<p>Small but Significant</p>	<p>Refers to how participants perceive the events' societal influence as modest in size but meaningful in effect, often describing ripple effects or long-term cultural shifts.</p>	<p>“Yes, as much as a single small or larger thing can so yes, it is the reflection effect that comes from it. Yes, but with what weighting? I do not see a revolution in it. But I see that it can be extremely important on an individual level. Then it will be interesting to see to what extent it visible then, for example, at the stage when young guys like this, who learn to deal with emotions to talk about feelings enter a relationship? How does it begin to appear in parenting? How it will be seen in future generations.” (<i>John, l. 36</i>)</p>
<p>Role of Women</p>	<p>Captures participants’ reflections on the role women have played in their emotional lives and in relation to the community. Includes statements about women being easier to talk to emotionally, women introducing them to the community (e.g. partners), and thoughts about how women could benefit from a similar space. Highlights how gendered experiences shape</p>	<p>“It has been easier to have these types of conversations with female friends.” (<i>Anton, l. 33</i>)</p>

	emotional support systems and community access.	
External Reactions	<p>Describes how participants' friends, family, or acquaintances have reacted when they've spoken about attending the events.</p> <p>Includes both supportive and skeptical reactions, surprise, encouragement, or judgment.</p>	<p>"Well mainly good. Especially face to face. Of course, some men do not feel an innate need for these emotional discussions, and these people usually are a bit scared of it because it becomes a quite timid and vulnerable feeling. Then again on Threds I've noticed that some commenter has been triggered and gone defensive. They've gone out to challenge the idea that why should men do emotional work, so yes there is certainly resistance in the deep ranks of the nation, but for the most part the feedback is good." (<i>Oliver, l. 32</i>)</p>
Challenges	<p>Describes the difficulties faced in influencing others, particularly those with entrenched or negative attitudes toward emotional openness or masculinity. This could include challenges in reaching those who are resistant to the changes the events promote, getting enough publicity and support for the community, and being accessible to all men despite location.</p>	<p>"There is the challenge that we who go there are not necessarily the ones who need to be heard and need to share our experiences the most. We are part of the social change, but the challenge is how to involve those who maintain problematic attitudes, for example towards women or work or egocentric thinking. Because they are the ones who will start a larger change, if they understand the need to change their behaviour." (<i>Tim, l. 38</i>)</p>

Appendix 4 – Interview consent form

Declaration of Consent

I, _____, declare that I am willing to participate in the interview as part of the master's thesis with the title “From Silence to Dialogue: The Individual and Societal Impacts of Events by Jäbät ja Tunteet” of my own free will. I am aware that my participation in this interview is voluntary, and I have the unrestricted right to withdraw my participation at any time without giving reasons. I was informed in detail about the purpose and context of the interview. This interview is for academic research purposes only as part of the above-mentioned master's thesis. I understand that the information I share during the interview will be kept strictly confidential and will be made available to the reviewers or the study program director for examination purposes upon request. This group of persons is subject to data protection regulations. It is guaranteed that my identity will remain protected and that my personal data will be presented anonymously in all publications or presentations. I understand that I have the right to withdraw my consent and request the deletion of my data at any time during or after the interview.

Date: _____ Signature: _____

Appendix 5 – Quotes

	Original Quote	Translation
1	Huomasin heti sen että silloin kun tuli sisään niin uudet tyypit otettiin heti mukaan. Mulla on välillä semmoinen olo, että jos haluaa aloittaa jonkun harrastuksen ja menee johonkin harrastusporukkaan, niin siellä ei välttämättä tajuta huomioida niitä ekakertalaisia. Niin mulle se ainakin heti loi sen hyvän fiiliksen että tulen uudestaan, koska siellä heti kysyttiin just että ootko sä ekaa kertaa ja selitettiin mitä tulee tapahtumaan. Semmoinen lämminhenkisyys oli se mikä tuli mieleen ja tuolla oli myös tosi helppo saada kavereita heti.	I noticed right away that when new guys came, they were immediately taken in very well. I sometimes have the feeling that if you go to a hobby group, they don't necessarily take the newbies into account that well. Here they immediately asked whether I was there for the first time and explained what would happen, which created the feeling that I would come again. It was this kind of warm-heartedness and it was also really easy to make friends straight away.
2	Mulla oli semmoinen mielikuva muodostunut sosiaalisen median perusteella, että siellä on vaan sellaisia helsinkiläispoikia, jotka on 10 vuotta tutkinut itseään ja puhunut tunteista ja ne on niin taitavia, että onko mulla mitään annettavaa ja pystynkö mä osallistumaan niihin keskusteluihin, että onko mun tunnetaidot sillä tasolla? Kaikkea tällaista pyöri mielessä.	I had this image based on social media that there are just guys from Helsinki who have spent 10 years studying themselves and talking about emotions and they are so skilled that I have nothing to give. Could I even participate in the discussions, are my emotional skills at that level? All these things were going through my mind.
3	Onneksi mä vähän valitsin se mun ensimmäisen conversation klubin sillain, että se oli semmoinen että me katsottiin elokuva ja puhuttiin siitä. Koen että se oli tosi hyvä tapahtuma ensikertalaiselle, ja olen sanonut jälkeinpäin, että vastaavanlaisia pitäisi pitää ja	Luckily, I kind of chose my first Conversation Club to be one where we watched a movie and then talked about the themes of the movie. I feel that it was a really good event for first-timers, and I have said afterwards that similar events should be held and advertised, as an easy way to get involved.

	mainostaa, että se on helppo tapa tulla mukaan toimintaan.	
4	<p>Ensimmäisillä parilla kerralla mulla oli vähän vieras olo siellä. En ihan päässyt mukaan siihen semmoiseen jäbästely meininkiin. Siellä oli joukko niistä alkuperäisistä vetäjistä, jotka jotenkin ylläpitävät sellaista että ”ok me puhutaan tunteista, mutta me ollaan kovia jätkeä”. Ehkä minä en ole oikein kokenut helpoksi olla miesporukoissa tai miespuolisten kanssa. Niin mulla oli vähän vaikea päästä siihen aluksi mukaan. Ehkä se oli vaan joku semmoinen vastareaktio, koska sitten musta siellä on ollut kivaa käydä keskustelemassa ihmisten kanssa.</p>	<p>The first couple of times I was there, I felt a bit strange. I couldn't quite get into the dude thing. There were a bunch of the original leaders, who somehow maintain that ‘ok we talk about feelings, but we are tough guys’. Maybe I haven't really found it easy to be in male groups or with males. So I had a bit of a hard time getting into it at first. Maybe it was just a kind of an initial reaction, because then I've enjoyed talking to people there.</p>
5	<p>Koska siellä on vain miehiä niin on helpompi tavallaan ymmärtää muiden tarinoita, ja ongelmia ja onnistumisiakin. Se auttaa niin kun sen keskustelun ylipäättään onnistumiseen ja niin kun ylläpitämiseen, että on ajatusmaailma ehkä jollain tavalla samanlainen, kun ollaan miehiä ja maskuliinisia ihmisiä.</p>	<p>Because it's all men it's easier to sort of understand other people's stories, and problems and successes. It helps the conversation in general to succeed when the way of thinking is perhaps in some way similar when you are all men and masculine people.</p>
6	<p>Mun mielestä se oli tosi hienoa, miten niin avoimesti muut uskalsivat ja miten siinä sitten itsekin uskalsi lähteä kaikkia asioita avaamaan. Mulla tuli siitä ensimmäisestä kerrasta semmoinen olo, niin kuin tämä olisi kaveriporukka mikä mulla on</p>	<p>I thought it was really cool how openly others dared and how I dared to open up myself. From that first time, I felt as if this was a group of friends that I had all along but didn't know about. I felt so at home and secure. It was really cool that it was so open.</p>

	koko ajan ollut. Mutta en ole vaan tiennyt siitä. Tuli niin kotoisa ja hyvä olla. Se oli tosi siistiä, kun se oli niin avointa.	
7	Siellä on aina ihmisiä, jotka puhuvat tosi vaikeista asioista mielellään ja se on mun mielestä tosi virkistävää, vaikka toki ymmärrä minkä takia ihmiset ei tee niin varsinkin tuntemattomien kanssa. Se on pelottavaa.	There are always people there who are happy to talk about really difficult things and I find that really refreshing, even though I understand why people don't do that and especially with strangers. It's scary.
8	Onhan toi vuorovaikutus aivan täysin poikkeuksellista mun mielestä.	I think the interactions at these events are quite extraordinary.
9	Minulla ei ole ollut hirveästi miespuolisia kavereita ja on tuntunut, että vaikea muodostaa kaverisuhteita muiden miesten kanssa. [...] Se voi johtua siitä, että miehiin tutustuminen on niin vaikeaa, kun se on aluksi niin pinnallista ja sitten en ole päässytäkään sinne syvään päätyyn niin nopeasti kuin itse kaipaaisin kaverisuhteilta.	I haven't had that many male friends and have found it difficult to form friendships with other men. [...] It could be because it is so difficult to get to know men, because it is so superficial at first and then I haven't got to the deep end as quickly as I would like to in a friendship.
10	(...) miesten kesken tapahtumien ulkopuolella mun mielestä noihin kaikkiin kanssakäymisiin hiipii semmoinen pieni tai vähän isompikin kilpailullisuus. Se on varmaan toksisen maskuliinisuuden yksi tällöinen kulmakivi semmoinen vertailu ja kilpailullisuus, ja sitä tulee tosi usein miesten välisistä keskusteluista jollain tasolla.	(...) among men outside these events, I think there's a small or even bigger competitiveness creeping into all those interactions. It is probably one of the cornerstones of toxic masculinity, this type of comparison and competitiveness, and it comes very often in conversations between men on some level.
11	(...) se vaikeus on tullut sitten ehkä miesten välisissä suhteissa. Niissä se on tuntunut vaikeammalta. Lähinnä ehkä, että	(...) the difficulty (in talking about feelings) has perhaps come in the relationships between men. In those it has felt more difficult. It doesn't mean

	<p>se ei tarkoita, etteikö mun elämässä olisi ollut aikaisemmin sellaisia miehiä, jotka olisi ollut varsin valmiita keskustelemaan tuollaisista teemoista, mutta enemmänkin siitä, että siihen ei oltu ehkä annettu samalla tavalla mahdollisuutta.</p>	<p>that there haven't been men in my life who would have been quite ready to discuss such topics, but more so because we haven't been given the same opportunity.</p>
12	<p>(...) arkikeskusteluissa miesten kanssa ei aina tiedä kuinka paljon se toinen on valmis puhumaan asioista ja kuinka paljon se on valmis kuuntelemaan muiden asioista.</p>	<p>(...) in everyday conversations with men you do not always know how much the other is willing to talk about things and how much they are willing to listen to others.</p>
13	<p>Jotenkin nyt hirvittää nähdä missä tilanteessa ollaan yhteiskunnallisesti. Hetki sitten puhuttiin fyysisestä väkivallasta ja siellä oli nuorisojärjestön edustaja semmoisessa paneelikeskustelussa. Puhuttiin siitä, miten väkivalta edelleen näkyy kaduilla ja konservatiivisia arvoja näkyy nuorten keskuudessa paljon. Huomaan että aika kahtiajakautunut, polarisoitunut yhteiskunta ja Jäbät ja Tunteet on sitten siellä toisella puolen sitä jakoa.</p>	<p>It's kind of scary to see where we are as a society. Recently we were talking about physical violence and there was a representative from a youth organization in a panel discussion. They talked about how violence is still visible on the streets and how conservative values are seen a lot among young people. I can see that society is quite divided and polarized, and Jäbät ja Tunteet are on the other side of that division.</p>
14	<p>(...) itsellä saattaa olla tosi vaikea aihe, ja sitten kun kuulee, jonkun toisen näkökulman ja että miten hän on päässyt siitä yli, niin sitten siinä tulee semmoinen ahaa elämys itsellekin, että voi hitsi että tämän asian voi katsoa myös tältä kantilta.</p>	<p>(...) hearing someone talk about a difficulty you experience yourself and how he has overcome it, becomes an awakening experience, that oh my gosh you can also look at it from this point of view.</p>
15	<p>Joo mun tapa nähdä tai suhtautua ihmisiin on muuttunut sillä tavalla, että se on oikeasti</p>	<p>My way of seeing or relating to people has changed. It has really surprised me that there are such young, street-credible, good-looking guys who are</p>

	<p>yllättävää, että siellä on semmoisia nuoria katu-uskottavia, komeita tyyppejä jotka puhuvat hirveän herkästi ja puhuu tunteista ja on hyvin avoimia ja miettii asioita ja on haavoittuvaisia. Eli siinä mielessä se on laajentunut mieskäsitystä tai mieskuvaa. Joo se on kauhean lohdullista ja se on aivan ihanaa jotenkin huomattava, että ihmisistä ei oikeasti tiedä koskaan päällepäin, että mitä se on hyvässä eikä pahassa, mutta ehkä ennen kaikkea ihmiset osaavat yllättää positiivisesti hirveän paljon.</p>	<p>highly sensitive, open, reflective, vulnerable, and talkative. In that sense it's a broadening of the concept of men or the image of men. It's so comforting and absolutely wonderful to notice that you never really know what's good or bad about people, but perhaps above all, people can surprise you positively an awful lot.</p>
16	<p>Tottakai ensimmäinen kerta jännitti ihan super paljon, mutta vielä pitkään sen jälkeen oli sellainen pieni jännitys päällä. (...) Nykyään, tai ehkä viimeiset, 5, 6, 7 kertaa ei ole enää jännittänyt niin paljoa, vaan se jännitys on vaihtunut innostukseen, koska toiminta ja porukka on sen verran tuttua.</p>	<p>Of course the first time I was super nervous, but for a long time afterwards there was still a little bit of nerves. (...) Nowadays, or maybe the last 5, 6, 7 times, there hasn't been so much nerves anymore, but that nerves have been replaced by enthusiasm, because the event and the people are so familiar.</p>
17	<p>Ei minua enää jännitä. Mutta siis kyllä minua jännitti siellä joo aluksi. Joo tai silleen varmaan aika montakin kertaa. Että siinä on ehkä kesti jonkun aikaa ennen kuin silleen rentoutu, mutta nyt se on luontevampaa, kun siellä on käynyt sen verran monta kertaa.</p>	<p>I'm not nervous anymore. But I mean, I was nervous there at first. I guess quite a few times. It might have taken me a while to relax, but now it's more natural, because I've been there so many times.</p>
18	<p>Yleensä sen jälkeen on tosi helpottunut olo ja hyvä olla. Mutta sitten välillä on myöskin</p>	<p>Usually after the event I have a relieved feeling and a sense of ease. But sometimes I also feel empty, so to</p>

	<p>niin sanotusti takki tyhjä.</p> <p>Osa näistä aiheista on semmoisia raskaampia tai on käyty vähän syvemmällä ja jos siellä on ollut jotain oikeasti vähän rankempaa asiaa, niin silloin ne ovat tietysti vähän sitten ottaakin. Ei nyt niin että ne kuluttaisivat, mutta ne tuntuvat vähän semmoiselta terapiasessiolta jälkikäteen.</p>	<p>speak. Some of these topics are a bit heavier or go deeper and if there has been something a bit harder, then the feeling might be different. I wouldn't say I feel worn out, but I feel a bit like I would after a therapy session.</p>
19	<p>Musta se on ollut tosi kiva paikka, jonne on voinut mennä juttelemaan. Kyllä se on tuonut selvästi jotain hyvää ja arvokasta mun elämään.</p> <p>Joissakin tilanteissa se on tuntunut tosi hyödylliseltä resurssilta, jos on ollut vaikka semmoinen olo, että haluaisi jutella jostain tai tulla kuulluksi tai ylipäätään haluaisi olla ihmisten kanssa. Jos on vaikka ollut yksinäinen olo, ettei ole kauheasti ollut ihmiskontakteja niin sitten toi on ollut tosi helppo paikka, jonne mennä ja nähdä ihmisiä ja jutella ihmisten kanssa.</p>	<p>I think it's been a really nice place to go and talk. It has clearly brought something good and valuable into my life. In some situations, it has felt like a really useful resource, if I've been feeling like I want to talk about something or be heard or just want to be with people in general. If I've been lonely and haven't had a lot of human contact, then this has been an easy place to go and see people and talk to people.</p>
20	<p>Ja just se, että kun kaikki saa puhua ja kaikkia kuunnellaan, niin sekin on just tosiaan ollut tärkeää.</p>	<p>Just the fact that everyone gets to talk and everyone is listened to has been important.</p>
21	<p>Mä muistan, että meillä oli kerran seksi aiheinen Conversation Club. Se jännitti tosi paljon, mutta se oli oikeasti tosi arvokas se koko keskustelu, koska en mä ollut ikinä käynyt sen tyyppistä keskustelua. Se todella jäi mieleen.</p>	<p>I remember that we had a sex-themed Conversation Club once. It was nerve-racking, but it was really valuable, because I had never had that kind of conversation before. It really stuck in my mind.</p>
22	<p>Tiedätkö kun pääsee kuulemaan muiden tarinoita tietyn aihepiirin</p>	<p>You know, when you get to hear other people's stories around a certain topic,</p>

	ympäriä, niin sitten siinä aina oppii ja näkee erilaisia näkökulmia.	you always learn and see different perspectives on things.
23	Tajusi sen, että jos tästä asiasta ei puhu niin muut ei sitä tiedä ja sitten maailma ei lähde siihen suuntaan mihin me halutaan sen lähtevän. Kyllähän siitä täytyy puhua ja kertoa. Taisin ensimmäiseksi kertoa omille vanhemmille. Ja sitten lähisukulaisille ja ystäville. Sitten mulla on semmoinen ydin poikakaveriporukka ollut ihan armeijan ajoista asti. Niin itse asiassa niistä yksi kaveri jopa tuli mukaan sinne seuraavalla kerralla.	I also realised that if you don't talk about it, others won't know about it and then the world won't go in the direction we want it to go. Of course we have to talk about it and tell people about it. I think the first thing I did was to tell my own parents. And then close relatives and friends. I've had a core group of male friends since I was in the army who I also told. In fact, one of them even joined the last Conversation Club.
24	Yhdelle läheiselle kaverille olen kertonut, että tulee käytyä näissä tapahtumissa. Joillakin ihmisillä saattaa nopeasti nousta jotain ennakkoluuloja pelkästään siitä, kun ne kuulevat, että Jäbät ja Tunteet on yhteisön nimi. On jotenkin helpompi vaan olla mainostamatta sitä kovin äänekkäästi.	I've told a close friend that I go to these events, but not others. Some people may quickly get some preconceptions just from hearing that Jäbät ja Tunteet is the name of the community. It is somehow easier just not to advertise it very loudly.
25	Isyys sen takia koska siitä ei myöskään miesten kesken juuri puhuta. Naisilta kun kuulee paljon sitä, että heiltä kysellään näistä lisääntymisasiosta jopa lapsesta lähtien ja miehet ei välttämättä ole puhunut kolmekymppisenäkään vielä kertaakaan, kun ei kukaan ole kysynyt, niin se on ihan äärimmäisen tärkeää siis yhteiskunnallisella tasolla. Aivan valtavan tärkeä juttu, että miehiltäkin nyt kysyttäisi joskus edes asiasta.	Fatherhood (was an important topic) because it's not much talked about among men. You hear a lot from women that they are asked about reproductive issues since childhood and men may be in their thirties without having ever spoken about it, since no one has asked, so it is extremely important at a social level. It is a very important thing that men should be asked sometimes.

26	<p>(...) pyrin myös omalla avoimuudella rohkaisemaan muitakin puhumaan ja jakamaan merkityksellisiä asioita arkipäivän tilanteissa, vaikka työpaikalla lounaalla. Ja kun puhun tunteista niin ei ne aina tarvitse olla mitään vaikeita negatiivisia juttuja vaan se voisi olla myös vaikka asioita mitkä on tuonut iloa tai onnea.</p>	<p>(...) with this openness I try to encourage others to talk and share meaningful things in everyday situations, for example at lunch at work. And when I talk about feelings, they don't always have to be difficult negative things, but could also be things that have brought you joy or happiness.</p>
27	<p>Monesti ollaan juteltu myös esimerkiksi siitä miten omassa kaveripiirissä saatetaan suhtautua maskuliinisuuteen ja miehisyyteen. Monet on sitten alkanut jopa haastamaan omien vanhojen kaveriporukoiden näkemyksiä ja yrittänyt vähän tuoda sitä Conversation Clubien sanomaa sinnekin.</p>	<p>Many times we have also talked about, for example, how people in our own circle of friends might view masculinity. Many have even started to challenge the views of their own old groups of friends and tried to bring a bit of the Conversation Clubs' message to them.</p>
28	<p>Minä olen huomannut, että varsinkin vanhemmat ystävyysuhteet, ne jotka on muodostunut vaikka teini iällä, niin niissä se tunteista puhuminen se ei ollut läsnä, niin se on haastavampaa lähteä niitä suhteita viemään sitten sitä kohti, että nyt voikin puhua tunteista.</p>	<p>I have noticed that especially with older friendships, those that have been formed as teenagers, when talking about feelings was not present, it is more challenging to take them towards a place where you can talk about feelings.</p>
29	<p>Uskon että tämä on merkittävä juttu monelle. Vaikka se ei nyt mitenkään sataisi heti laariin, mutta tämä todennäköisesti tönäisee aika monta itseäni vähän nuorempaa miestä ja toivottavasti myös niitä parinkymppin kieppeillä olevia miehiä niin semmoisille poluille että ne osaavat jättää ne ahdistavat miesihanteet pois elämästään.</p>	<p>I think it's a significant thing for many people. Even if we can't necessarily pick the fruits of it right away, but this probably pushes quite a few men younger than myself and hopefully also those men around their twenties to paths where they know how to leave those oppressive male ideals out of their lives.</p>

30	<p>Siinä on sellainen haaste, että me jotka käydään siellä ei välttämättä olla niitä, joiden nimenomaan täytyisi tulla kuulluksi ja täytyisi päästä jakamaan elämään. Että me ollaan kyllä osa kulttuurimuutosta, mutta haaste on se, että miten he, jotka ylläpitävät ongelmallista suhtautumista, vaikka naisiin tai työelämään tai egosentriseen ajatteluun, niin miten he saataisiin mukaan?</p>	<p>There is the challenge that we who go there are not necessarily the ones who need to be heard and need to share our experiences the most. We are part of the social change, but the challenge is how to involve those who maintain problematic attitudes, for example towards women or work or egocentric thinking.</p>
31	<p>Joo siinä missä nyt joku niin kuin yksittäinen pieni tai isompi asia voi niin joo, kyllä sanotaan, että kyllä siinä on se heijastus efekti mikä siitä tulee. Joo, mutta millä painoarvolla? En minä siinä vallankumousta näe. Mutta muuten näen sen yksilön kannalta ihan äärimmäisen merkittävänä ja se sitten, että millä että se heijastuisi niin missä määrin se rupeaa näkymään sitten esimerkiksi siinä vaiheessa, kun tämmöiset nuoret kaverit, jotka oppivat käsittelemään tunteita puhumaan tunteista. Ja miten se rupeaa näkymään parisuhteessa? Miten se rupeaa näkymään vanhemmuudessa?</p>	<p>Yes, as much as a single small or larger thing can so yes, it is the reflection effect that comes from it. But with what weighting? I do not see a revolution in it. But I see that it can be extremely important on an individual level. Then it will be interesting to see to what extent it is visible, for example, at the stage when young guys like this who have learned to process and talk about their feelings enter a relationship? How does it begin to appear in parenting?</p>
32	<p>Keskustelun luonne tuossa yhteisössä tai ainakin Telegrammissa on jonkin verran ratkaisukeskeistä. Minä-keskeistä mun mielestä, mikä mulla tökkii siinä. Minulle siinä on semmoisia kaikuja, että keskitytään minuun ja minun hyvään pointtiin, siinä</p>	<p>The nature of the discussion in this community, or at least on Telegram, is somewhat solution-oriented. Me-centric in my opinion, which is what I find troublesome about it. For me it has echoes that focus on me and my good, where I think it is more interesting to think about how I can be better for others. But I think it's necessary for</p>

	<p>missä mun mielestä on kiinnostavampaa ajatella, että miten voin olla parempi muita kohtaan. Mutta se on varmaan ihan tarpeellista monelle, että pitää saada oma setti kasaan ensin kunnolla.</p>	<p>many people to get their own shit together properly first.</p>
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